

BOOK OF ABSTRACT

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON HEALTH SCIENCE 2021

THE 8 - ICHS
SEPTEMBER 23-24,
2021

PREFACE

The 8th International Conference on Health Sciences 2021 (ICHS 2021) is organized by Politeknik Kesehatan Kementerian Kesehatan Yogyakarta in collaboration with PUINOVAKESMAS, Politeknik Kesehatan Kementerian Kesehatan Denpasar, Politeknik Kesehatan Kementerian Banjarmasin, Politeknik Kesehatan Kementerian Palu, Politeknik Kesehatan Kementerian Palembang, Politeknik Kesehatan Kementerian Pangkal Pinang, PUI-PK Poltekkes Kemenkes Ternate, Universitas Medika Suherman, AKG Mataram. Akpek “YKY” Yogyakarta, and St. Paul University Philipines. We would like to thank the sponsors in these conferences, namely BNI 46, FDC Dental Care, and Integritas. We also like to thank the professional organizations, namely PATELKI, IBI, PPNI, HAKLI, PERSAGI, and also PTGMI.

ICHS 2021 is aimed in providing the forum of scientific communication and interaction among distinguished scientists working in the health area and its related fields. In this scientific event the latest research results will present the state-of-the-art development in the field and help to guide our future research directions. It is also designed to offer the opportunity of making direct contacts for all researchers in Indonesia and abroad and thereby fostering the existing research collaborations and extending international research networking for the future. The scope of research results have been presented and discussed in this symposium covers nursing, public health, nutrition, midwifery, medical laboratory technology, environmental health, medical record and information health system and also oral and dental health care.

The program of ICHS 2021 features, 2 Keynote speech, 10 invited talks and 78 contributed oral presentations, which come from 3 different countries: Turkey, Philipines and Indonesia. All papers have been reviewed after they are presented in this event. Papers will be published in Proceeding or in a Journal (National and International). Finally, I would like to express my sincere appreciation to all of authors for their valuable contributions and also to the members of the committee for their excellent works in preparing and finalizing this conference and document.

Yogyakarta, September 2021

Chairman of ICHS 2021,

Dr. Agus Kharmayana Rubaya, M.PH

GREETINGS FROM CO-HOST PARTNERS

Assalamualaikum Wr. Wb

My best regards to all of you, ladies and gentlemen.

I am Triseu Setianingsih, Chancellor of Suherman Medika University.

We Would like to Say thank u for Poltekkes Yogyakarta for the opportunity for us, **Universitas Medika Suherman** to participate in The 8th International Conference on Health Science 2021. We firmly believe that this international Conference can be the best event for all lecturers and students to share valuable knowledge. In addition, excellent collaboration between universities brings excellent achievements in increasing the role of universities in disseminating knowledge and providing solutions to current problems. We also express our gratitude to all the speakers from St. Paul University Philippines, MoH Republic of Indonesia, WHO-Indonesia, Griffith University, Deakin University-Australia, Attaturk University_Turkey, The Academy of Occupational And Environmental Medicine_Malaysia

We hope that this collaboration can continue in broader activities such as joint research, lecturer and student exchanges, visiting professors, internships and so on.

Hopefully, the role of education will be wider and develop in the dissemination of knowledge and improving the quality and welfare of people in the world.

thanks and success to all the teams who have collaborated to organize this activity well.

Wassalamualaikum. Wr. Wb

Assalamualaikum warahmatullahi wabarakatuh,

On behalf of Health Polytechnic of Ternate, allow me to express my happy feeling to Health Polytechnic of Jogjakarta and all co-hosts who have played an active role so that this international conference event can run smoothly and very well.

The Health Polytechnic of Ternate strongly supports the implementation of the entire series of 8th international conference on health science activities. Hopefully, Health Polytechnic of Jogjakarta and Health Polytechnic of Ternate will always be able to work together in all fields. Health Polytechnic of Ternate has tried to establish sustainable partnerships with various parties and always take opportunities at any time for the development of Health Polytechnic in the future. Research results published through the 8th international conference on health science are very up-to-date and easy to apply. This fact also makes the Health Polytechnic of Ternate feel that this activity can provide benefits for the development of science and technology in Indonesia.

To all parties who have played an active role in organizing the 8th ICHS activity, we express our gratitude and appreciation for their hard work and smart work. More specifically, we thank Polkesyo as the main organizer of the activity.

Finally, allow us to promote cultural greetings and thanks in Ternate language, namely "Suba Jou" and "Syukur Dofu-Dofu"

Director of Health Polytechnic of Ternate

Rusny Muhammad S.Pd., M.Kes

Assalamualaikum Wr. Wb.

Good morning, ladies and Gentlemen. First of all, on behalf of the Health Polytechnic Ministry of Health Banjarmasin, I would like to say thank you very much and appreciate to the Health Polytechnic Ministry of Health Yogyakarta who conduct the 8th International Conference on Health Science (ICHS) and I am proud that the Health Polytechnic Ministry of Health Banjarmasin becomes co-Host in this international conference.

There are many advantages obtained from this international conference. We can share and update knowledge, research, and build collaboration with universities and many experts that follow this international conference. We can facilitate our lecturers to share and improve their researches. I would like to express my proudness for the Health Polytechnic Ministry of Health Banjarmasin's lecturers who gain opportunities to present their researches here. And for our participants, I would say welcome and take advantage to improve your researches future. I hope, this collaboration can continue in the following years.

Thank you very much.

Dr. H. Mahpolah, M.Kes

Director of Health Polytechnic Ministry of Health Banjarmasin

Assalamu alaikum warahmatullahi wabarakatuh
Good morning, ladies and gentlemen. First of all, on behalf of the Palu Health Polytechnic

I would like to express my appreciation to the Yogyakarta Health Polytechnic who generously initiated the 8th International Conference on Health Science. In this conference, I believe there are many benefits that we will achieve because we have the opportunity to share knowledge, exchange experiences and discussions related to research and network with public health experts. It will also give us the opportunity to hear some of the world's best inspirational keynote speakers. As a result, it will be more interesting compared to the experience of knowledge. I believe this conference will help us build our competence in the health field and branding our expertise.

I thank Yogyakarta Health Polytechnic for giving us Palu Health Polytechnic the opportunity to be a co-host of the conference. I want to say once again on behalf of the co-host of this conference, welcome. It's great to have all of you as participants and experts here. Stay healthy and happy.

Director,

Nasrul, SKM, M.Kes
Polytechnic of Health Palu

Good morning, ladies and gentlemen. First of all, on behalf of the Polytechnic of Health Denpasar, I would like to express my appreciation to the Polytechnic of Health Yogyakarta who generously initiated the 8th International Conference on Health Science.

In this conference, there are many benefits as we would have the opportunity to share knowledge, exchange research discussion and to network with public health experts. This also will provide us the opportunity to listen world best inspiring keynote speakers in the field. As a result, it will be more attractive compared to knowledge experiences. I believe this conference will help you build your competences in health and branding your expertise.

Thank you very much for giving us to be co-host of the conference. I would like to say once more on behalf of co-host this conference, welcome. It is great to have you all as participants and experts here. Stay healthy and safe.

Director,

Dr. Anak Agung Ngurah Kusumajaya, SP., MPH.
Polytechnic of Health Denpasar

I am, Tri Arini, the Director of Akper YKY Yogyakarta, as one of the Co-Hosts at the Conference on Health Sciences (ICHS), would like to thank you for your cooperation at the 2021 Conference on Health Sciences (ICHS) organized by Poltekkes, Ministry of Health Yogyakarta.

This conference is one of the commitment forms to realizing the Tri Dharma of Higher Education. A series of activities were carried out to increase the participants' knowledge about various health and nursing sciences and increase the number of publications from various Indonesia regions and other participating countries.

Hopefully, the cooperation activities in the organization of this international conference can be carried out continuously.

Director of Akper YKY Yogyakarta

Tri Arini, S.Kep, Ns., M.Kep

CONFERENCE PROGRAM

Schedule for The 8th International Conference on Health Sciences 2021

Day / Date	Time (Indonesia Time GMT +7 / WIB)	Main Room	Room 1	Room 2	Room 3	Room 4
Day 1 Thursday, 23 September	07.00 – 07.30	Registration				
	07.30 – 08.00	Opening Remarks: 1. St. Paul University 2. Poltekkes Kemenkes Yogyakarta				
	08.00 – 08.15	Welcome speech: MoH Republic of Indonesia				
	08.15 – 08.30	Video Profile from Partners				
	08.30 – 10.00	“Healthy Cities and Inequities” <i>(Dr. Tara M Kessaram – Healthier Population/Non- Communicable Disease Team Leader - WHO Indonesia)</i> <i>Moderator: Dr. Maria Elizabet C Baua (St. Paul University- Philippines)</i>				
	10.00 – 10.30		Video Profile from Partners	Video Profile from Partners	Video Profile from Partners	Video Profile from Partners

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Day / Date	Time (Indonesia Time GMT +7 / WIB)	Main Room	Room 1	Room 2	Room 3	Room 4
	10.30 – 11.30		<p>“Environmental Factors That Influence COVID-19 Spread” <i>Dicky Budiman Ph.D (Griffith University)</i></p> <p>Moderator: Dr. Agus Kharmayana R (Poltekkes Kemenkes Yogyakarta)</p>	<p>“Healthy Food Environment” <i>Prof. Anna Peeters (Deakin Univ-Australia)</i></p> <p>Moderator: Dr. Badrut Tamam, M.Biotech (Poltekkes Kemenkes Denpasar)</p>	<p>“Role of Midwife in Health City” <i>Prof. Serap EA (Ataturk Univ-Turkey)</i></p> <p>Moderator: Hesty Widiasih, M.Keb (Poltekkes Kemenkes Yogyakarta)</p>	<p>“Healthy Workplace: Prevention of Occupational Cancer” <i>Prof. Marzuki bin Isahak (The Academy of Occupational and Environmental Medicine-Malaysia)</i></p> <p>Moderator: Muliyadi M.KL (Poltekkes Kemenkes Ternate)</p>
	11.30 – 12.00		Discussion	Discussion	Discussion	Discussion
	12.00 – 13.00		Break	Break	Break	Break
	13.00 – 16.00		<p><i>Oral Presentation</i> Moderator Ns. Furaida Khasanah M.Kep</p> <p>Operator: Melita</p> <p>PIC: Devy Kurniaramadhani, S.ST</p>	<p><i>Oral Presentation</i> Moderator Almira Sitasari, M.PH</p> <p>PIC: Erika Wahyu Widyastuti, S.Tr.Gz Operator: Patrya</p>	<p><i>Oral Presentation</i> Moderator Dwiana Estiwidani, M.Kes</p> <p>PIC: Menik Kasiyati, M.Imun Operator: Sefia</p>	<p><i>Oral Presentation</i> Moderator Siti Hani I, M.Kes</p> <p>PIC: Lilis Setyaningsih, S.Tr.Gz Operator: Sefia</p>

BOOK OF ABSTRACT

Day / Date	Time (Indonesia Time GMT +7 / WIB)	Main Room	Room 1	Room 2	Room 3	Room 4
Day 2	08.00 – 09.00	Registration				
Friday, 24 September	09.00 – 10.30	<p>“Covid-19 Pandemic: Lessons Learned and Future Direction in The US from the Community Health Nursing Viewpoint” <i>Prof. Diane CM (University of Rhode Island-USA)</i></p> <p>Moderator: Dr. Catherine (St. Paul University Philipines)</p>				
	10.30 – 11.30		<p>“Recruiting COVID Convalescence Plasma (CCP) Donor During Pandemic: Challenge and Answer” <i>Dr. Ni Luh Putu Eka Sudiwati (Poltekkes Malang- Ind)</i></p> <p>Moderator: Heri Setyo Bkti, M.Biomed (Poltekkes Kemenkes Denpasar</p>	<p>“The Role of Nurse Anesthetists in Universal Health” <i>Jackie SR (International Federation of Nurse Anesthetist-USA)</i></p> <p>Moderator: Nurun Laasara, M.Kep (Poltekkes Kemenkes Yogyakarta)</p>	<p>“The Challenges to Nursing Education During Pandemic: Brunei Darussalam Perspective” <i>Prof. Armah Binti Tengah (Politeknik Brunei)</i></p> <p>Moderator: Fitriyanti N. Idrus M.Kep (Poltekkes Kemenkes Ternate)</p>	<p>“Medical Record Borrowing Control Tools Design: Tracer and Outguide” <i>Niko Tesni Saputro M.PH (Poltekkes Yogyakarta-Ind)</i></p> <p>Moderator: Sefi Hardianti, M.Pd (Poltekkes Kemenkes Yogyakarta)</p>
	11.30 – 12.00			Discussion	Discussion	Discussion
	12.00 – 13.00	Video Profile Partners				

Day / Date	Time (Indonesia Time GMT +7 / WIB)	Main Room	Room 1	Room 2	Room 3	Room 4
	13.00 – 14.30	<p>“The Role of Vocational Colleges in Realizing a Healthy City” <i>Wikan Sakarinto, Ph.D</i> (Directorate General of Vocational Higher Education)</p> <p>Moderator: Dr. Agus Kharmayana R (Poltekkes Kemenkes Yogyakarta)</p>				
	14.30 – 15.30 WIB		<p>“Anesthesia Nursing Education at the Health Polytechnic of the Ministry of Health Yogyakarta” <i>Bondan Palestin</i> (Poltekkes Yogyakarta-Ind)</p> <p>Moderator: Dr. Miriam (St. Paul University Philippines)</p>	<p>“A QoL of Toodler During Covid-19 Pandemic from a Health Promotion Perspective towards Healthy City” <i>Dr. Heni PW</i> (Poltekkes Yogyakarta-Ind)</p> <p>Moderator: Dr. Jeremy Godofredo C Morales (St. Paul University Philippines)</p>	<p>“The Roles of Oral Health Therapist in Healthy Urban Community” <i>Zaini Dahlan</i> (Indonesian Oral Health Therapist Association)</p> <p>Moderator: Rizki Amanullah, MH.Kes (Poltekkes Kemenkes Yogyakarta)</p>	
	15.30 – 15.45		Discussion	Discussion	Discussion	Discussion
	15.45 – 17.00		<p>Oral Presentation Moderator Ns. Furaida Khasanah M.Kep</p>	<p>Oral Presentation Moderator Almira Sitasari, M.PH</p>	<p>Oral Presentation Moderator Dwiana Estiwidani, M.Kes</p>	<p>Oral Presentation Moderator Siti Hani I, M.Kes</p>
	17.00 – 17.30	Closing Ceremony				

BOOK OF ABSTRACT

Day / Date	Time (Indonesia Time GMT +7 / WIB)	Main Room	Room 1	Room 2	Room 3	Room 4
		Best Presenter: Day 1 (4 presenter) Day 2 (4 Presenter)				
		Favourite Presenter: Day 1 (4 Presenter) Day 2 (4 Presenter)				

Room 1: Primrose Room (3rd Floor)				
Moderator : Ns. Furaida Khasahah, M.Kep				
PIC : Devy Kurnia Ramadhani, SST				
IT : Harsono				
Day 1 (Thursday, 23 September, 2021)				
No	Time	Author	Title	Section
1	13.00-13.10	St Paul University		
2	13.10-13.20	Sri Arini Winarti Rinawati, Wahyu Ratna, Induniasih	Implementation of TB active case finding by Puskesmas officers on the achievement of new TB case findings at DIY	Nursing and anesthesiology
3	13.20-13.30	Muhammad Faisal Pataha, Arsad Suni	Kiepoly: Volcano disaster mitigation media for teenagers containing local wisdom values of North Maluku Province	Nursing and anesthesiology
4	13.30-13.40	Ni Luh Kompyang Sulisnadewi, I Ketut Labir, Suratiah	Empowerment of family in giving massage therapy reduce complaints of acute respiratory tract infection in children	Nursing and anesthesiology
5	13.40-13.50	Rahmita Nuril Amalia, Tri Arini	The effect of story play therapy in language development children with mental retardation at SLB Rela Bhakti I, Gamping, Sleman, Yogyakarta, Indonesia	Nursing and anesthesiology
6	13.50-14.00	Titik Fajriyati Nur K, Maryana, RR. Sri Arini W. R	The influence of giving health education with The Smart Link application to increase knowledge of first aid in student of 1st State Senior High School of Godean	Nursing and anesthesiology
7	14.00-14.10	Nazliansyah, Ashar Abilowo	The Effect of Self-Efficacy and Subjective Norm in Motivating Handwashing Behavior among School Students in Coastal Area	Nursing and anesthesiology
8	14.10-14.20	Ni Komang Wardani, I Wayan Juni Arsana, Mahesa Dwipayani	Health promotion strategy through family approach and community empowerment for reducing the risk of non-communicable disease in Denpasar	Public Health
9	14.20-14.30	Joko Tigo Narimo Bekt, Maryana, Abiyu Naufal Susanto, Titik Fajriyati Nur Khasanah, Wahyu Febriana	The effect of health education with SINERGIS Disc Media on the knowledge level of self-management of Diabetes Mellitus patients in the elderly group at the Seyegan Health Center	Community Empowerment

10	14.30-14.40	Nyoman Ribek, Ni Luh Putri Kristina Meilani, NLP Yunianti S.C	The level of anxiety of senior high school adolescent during the COVID-19 pandemic	Nursing and anesthesiology
11	14.40-14.50	Aprilia Ega Suci Hartanti, Eko Suryani, Jullia Tri Winahyu, Dian Novita	The effect of website based e-poster health education on physical distancing anxiety in the Yogyakarta Ministry of Health Polytechnic Environment	Nursing and anesthesiology
12	14.50-15.00	Abiyyu Naufal Susanto, Maryana, Budhy Ermawan	The corelation of academic stress and academic workload with academic burnout during COVID-19 pandemic among Nursing Student in Health Polytechnic of the Ministry of Health in Yogyakarta	Nursing and anesthesiology
13	15.00-15.10	Ira Kusumawaty, Yunike, Lukman	Revealing the experience of nursing student in psychiatric hospital placement: hidden challenges in the COVID-19 era	Nursing and anesthesiology

Room 1

Day 2 (Friday, September 24, 2021)

No	Time	Author	Title	Section
1	15.45-15.52	St Paul University		
2	15.52-15.59	Wasis Nugroho, Aminudin Muhammad	Pattern in dealing with cardiac arrest in the environment family in North Maluku Province	Nursing and anesthesiology
3	15.59-16.06	Tenang Aristina, Nunung Rachmawati, Yayang Harigustian, Mahar Agusno	Literature review : the effectiveness of the sexual orientation change effort (SOCE) method for Egodistonic Homosexuality	Nursing and anesthesiology
4	16.06-16.13	Kusbaryanto, Sari	The effectiveness of handwashing education with audiovisual methods to increase student's knowledge and attitudes about handwashing at SMU Negeri 1 Gamping, Sleman, Yogyakarta	Public Health
5	16.13-16.20	Resy Asmalia, Thia Prameswarie, Chairunnisa Alya Ananda	The differences of hand washing with soap level knowledge before and after receiving health promotion about hand washing with soap in student at Pusri Junior High School	Community Empowerment
6	16.20-16.27	Barkah Wulandari, Apri Nur Wulandari	Model of reproductive health development in adolescent with special needs: intellectual disabilities based on teacher need assessment in Yogyakarta	Nursing and anesthesiology

7	16.27-16.34	Maulina Galuh Arifah, Bondan Palestin, Pramadita Elena, Juwita Putri Kartini, Doni Setiawan	NERD APPS: An anesthetic pharmacology learning media based application for anesthetist student during the COVID-19 Pandemic	Nursing and anesthesiology
8	16.34-16.41	Kania Ratna Arimbi, Bondan Palestine	Analysis online learning readiness in preparing for nursing anesthesia fieldwork competency practices	Nursing and anesthesiology

Room 2 : Lavender Room (3rd Floor)				
Moderator : Almira Sitasari, MPH				
PIC : Erika Wahyu Widyastuti, S.Tr.Gz				
IT : Gito				
Day 1 (Thursday, 23 September, 2021)				
1	13.00-13.10	Ni Putu Agustini, IGP Sudita Puryana, I Komang Agusjaya Mataram	Modificaation of traditional Balinese food as disaster emergency food	Nutrition and Dietetic
2	13.10-13.20	Badrut Tamam, I Gusti Putu Sudita Puryana	Potency of some foods as antiviral in protecting from COVID-19	Nutrition and Dietetic
3	13.20-13.30	Meilla Dwi Andrestian, Rizal Damanik, Faisal Anwar, Nancy Dewi Yuliana	The potential effect of Torbangun (<i>Coleus amboinicus</i> Lour) leaves extract in decreasing of blood glucose levels and glutathione peroxidation activities in hyperglycemic rat model	Nutrition and Dietetic
4	13.30-13.40	Prita Enggar Windarti, Idi Setiyobroto, Rini Wuri Astuti	Effect of giving flour combination formula red bean (<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> L) and breadfruit (<i>Artocarpus communis</i>) on body weight, feed intake and SCFA (Short Chain Fatty Acid) levels in diabetic rats	Nutrition and Dietetic
5	13.40-13.50	Mega Nurdini, Agus Wijanarka, Almira Sitasari	Mixed formula of red bean flour (<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i>) and breadfruit flour (<i>Artocarpus communis</i>) on blood lipid profile in diabetes rat inducted Streptozotosin- Nicotinamide (STZ-NA)	Nutrition and Dietetic
6	13.50-14.00	Ira Muslina, Nur Cahya Rachmawati, Zulya Erda, Nurul Aini Suria Saputri	Healthy drink Soya Zalacca (Soca) rich in iron and vitamin C as a drink for pregnant women	Nutrition and Dietetic
7	14.00-14.10	Yuli Hartati, Saprianto, Dika Febriyansari, Podojoyo, Afriyani Siregar, Imelda Telisa	Formulation and sensory properties of biscuit with Catfish substitution as an additional foods alternative for less nutritional children	Nutrition and Dietetic
8	14.10-14.20	Lely Cintari, DP Sukraniti	Implementation of transtheoretical model of nutrition education and chromium picolinate supplementation on dietary adherence behaviour, chromium consumption pattern and blood	Nutrition and Dietetic

			glucose level diabetes mellitus patients	
9	14.20-14.30	Ade Devriany, Endah Mayang Sari, Ori Pertamina Enardi, Emmy Kardinasari	The effect of fat intake on the adults central obesity in The Girimaya Health Center, Pangkalpinang	Nutrition and Dietetic
10	14.30-14.40	I Putu Suiroaka, Ni Komang Wiardani, Indhira Shagti	Development of BCD-Based Health Promotion Model (Benefit, Comparative, and Dangerous) improving adolescent resilience to exposure unhealthy food advertisements	Public Health
11	14.40-14.50	Novidiyanto, Sutyanawan	A comparative of antioxidant activity and total phenol between tea from a lowland plantation in Bangka Belitung Island and tea from commercial brands	Public Health
Room 2				
Day 2 (Friday, September 24, 2021)				
No	Time	Author	Title	Section
1	15.45-15.52	Siti Zainatun Wasilah, Bambang Supriyanto, Arma Wulan Mardhika	Comparison of Neutrophil to lymphocyte ratio (NLR) among negative and confirmed positive for COVID-19 patients at Yogyakarta Hospital	Medical Laboratory Technology
2	15.52-15.59	Ahmad Sukowaluyo, Anik Nuryati, Siti Zainatun Wasilah, Amanda Retma A	The difference of in the inhibition of essential oils of kenikir leaves (<i>Cosmos caudatus</i> Kunth.) and essential oils of kemangi leaves (<i>Ocimum basilicum</i>) on the growth of <i>Enterobacter aerogenes</i>	Medical Laboratory Technology
3	15.59-16.06	Siti Zainatun Wasilah, Budi Martono, Wahyu Adi Pratama	Potential of Keningkir (<i>Cosmos caudatus</i> Kenth) leaves essential oil against <i>Candida albicans</i> ATCC 10231 in vitro	Medical Laboratory Technology
4	16.06-16.13	Ajeng Ayuning Tyas, Suyana, Siti Zainatun Wasilah, Muhammad Burhanudin	Utilization of rice bran (<i>Oryza sativa</i> L.) situ bagendit variety as an alternative media for fungal growth <i>Trichophyton mentagrophytes</i>	Medical Laboratory Technology
5	16.13-16.20	Baiq Mutmainnah, Ni'matuzahroh, Afaf Baktir	Ethyl acetate and ethanol extract of leaf <i>Abrus precatorius</i> L. as inhibitors against Biofilm Formation <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> stains Methicillin resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (MRSA) 22372 Indonesia local Isolate	Medical Laboratory Technology
6	16.20-16.27	Supnawadi, Baiq Mutmainnah	Potential effect of ethyl acetate extract of <i>Mimosa pudica</i> L. against	Medical Laboratory Technology

			biofilm formation of Streptococcus mutants	
7	16.27-16.34	Podojoyo, Tria Erna Juliana, Susyani, Yuli Hartati, Muhamad Taswin, Zainal Abidin	Relationship consumption of macronutrients, body mass index, smoking status with physical fitness at Palembang Police District	Nutrition and Dietetic

Room 3				
Moderator: Dwiana Estiwidani, MPH				
PIC : Menik Kasiyati, M.Imun				
IT : Fuad Hasyim				
Day 1 (Thursday, 23 September, 2021)				
No	Time	Author	Title	Section
1	13.00-13.10	Elif Yağmur GÜR, Serap ÖZTÜRK ALTINAYAK	The relationship between the effect of pregnancy complaints on quality of life and the self perception level	Midwifery
2	13.10-13.20	Azniah Syam, Ashar HM, Eva Arna Abrar	Marital age, cigarette exposure, physical activity, sleep duration and prenatal depression	Public Health
3	13.20-13.30	Melly Damayanti, Maysarah	Utilization of the maternal child health book to maternal knowledge during the COVID-19 Pandemic	Midwifery
4	13.30-13.40	Heni Puji Wahyuningsih, Diani Fadmi Putri	Path analysis: Risk factors for asphyxia neonatorum	Midwifery
5	13.40-13.50	Aga Rahma Putri, Atik Badiah, Eko Suryani	The effect of health education about anticipatory guidance for breastfeeding mothers knowledge in preventing child malnutrition at working area of Puskesmas Mantrijeron Yogyakarta	Nursing and anesthesiology
6	13.50-14.00	Ni Wayan Armini, Gusti Ayu Marhaeni, I Gusti Ayu Surati, Ni Made Dwi Mahayati, Ni Wayan Suarniti, Ni Komang Erny Astiti, Ni Luh Putu Sri Erawati	SPEOS method (Stimulation of Endorphin Massage and Suggestive) activates let down reflex (LDR) of postpartum mother at Public Health Center Denpasar	Midwifery
7	14.00-14.10	Kharisma Virgian, Desy Setiawati, Rarnaningsih Dewi Astuti	Hypnobreastfeeding android application for woman breastfeeding anxiety	Midwifery
8	14.10-14.20	Ayi Diah Damayani, Eka Safitri Yanti	The different of maternal brain derived neurotrophic factor and total score Edinburg postnatal depression scale between low and normal ferritin among pregnant women	Midwifery

9	14.20-14.30	Ismi Nur Aini, Yuni Kusmiyati, Nanik Setiyawati	The relationship of anxiety with the accuracy of the 3-month injection contraception re-visit during the COVID-19 Pandemic in Sleman Regency	Midwifery
10	14.30-14.40	Rohani Siregar	Knowledge of teenage girls on breast self 20cupressure behavior (BSE)	Midwifery
11	14.40-14.50	Rahmita Nuril Amalia, Tri Arini, Viantika Kusumasari	The effect of 20cupressure technique on breast milk production postpartum mother at Rajawali Citra Hospital Yogyakarta Indonesia	Midwifery
12	14.50-15.00	Lutfiana Puspita Sari, Rosalinna	Decrease anxiety third trimester on pregnancy-impact on hypnobirthing	Midwifery
Room 3				
Day 2 (Friday, September 24, 2021)				
No	Time	Author	Title	Section
1	15.45-15.52	St Paul University		
2	15.52-15.59	Niken Meilani, Nanik Setiyawati	The effectiveness between peer educators and guidance counselling teachers to reproductive health level knowledge among senior high school girls students	Public Health
3	15.59-16.06	Siti Nur Annisa, Hesty Widyasih, Tri Maryani	Animation video “Anemia Rematri” and knowledge about anemia of girl adolescent	Midwifery
4	16.06-16.13	Nurdiana Lante, Istiana Asrari Bansu	Psychosocial stress with vaginal discharge of adolescent women in the new normal era in Bastiong Karance Village Ternate	Midwifery
5	16.13-16.20	Dewi Kusumaningtyas, Dwi Juwartini	Parent’s experience in giving reproductive health education to children	Nursing and anesthesiology
6	16.20-16.27	Ermaya Sari Bayu Ningsih	The impact of the dating scene on teenagers premarital sexual activity in Karawang Indonesia	Midwifery

Room 4: Lilac (3rd Floor)				
Moderator : Siti Hani Istiqomah, M.Kes				
PIC : Lilis Setyaningsih, S.Tr.Gz				
IT : Arif Rismawan				
Day 1 (Thursday, 23 September, 2021)				
No	Time	Author	Title	Section
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2	13.10-13.20	Dwi Wahyu Purwiningsih, Sakriani	The quality of compost using skipjack gill with anaerob method	Environmental Health
3	13.20-13.30	Ida Ayu Made Sri Arjani, Cok Dewi Widhya Hana Sundari, IGA Dhyana Putri, Ni Nengah Ariati	The use of seated grinder reduces complaints of musculoskeletal disorders, workload, and increases work productivity of Pandai Besi in Gubug Village, Tabanan Bali	Environmental Health
4	13.30-13.40	Purnama Sidebang	Occupational lung function impairment by particulate matter 2,5 (PM 2,5) exposure in fish smoking workers	Environmental Health
5	13.40-13.50	Rizqi Intan Wahyuni, Agus Kharmayana Rubaya, Yamtama	Mapping of DHF in Sleman Regency in 2015-2019 based on some indicators	Environmental Health
6	13.50-14.00	Hubullah Fuadzy, Heni Prasetyowati	Knowledge, attitude, and practice of dengue in Bandung City: Partial least squares structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM) techniques using SmartPLS	Environmental Health
7	14.00-14.10	Syarifah Nuraini, Sri Handayani, Paisal, Suharmiati	The challenges of improving sanitation in a community based intervention: study in Podok Village, South Kalimantan	Environmental Health
8	14.10-14.20	Eva Dewi R Purba, Rachmawati Felani Djuria, M. Seto Sudirman	The utilization of medicinal plants as a traditional drug in public women in the Mentok Subdistrict West Bangka Regency in 2020	Public Health
9	14.20-14.30	Aqsalsa Setya Sabila, Anton Kristijono, Niko Tresni Saputro	Medical record borrowing control tools design: tracer and outguide	Medical Record and Health Information

10	14.30-14.40	Afif Wahyudi Hidayat	Monitoring analysis of the speed of outpatient medical record services at Sentra Medika Cikarang Hospital Bekasi Regency 2021	Medical Record and Health Information
11	15.50-16.00	Sri Haryanti, Evi Gravitiani, Mahendra Wijaya, Adhy Timur Hartanto	Social Capital and Social Impact in Waste Management of the Waste Bank System in Yogyakarta Indonesia	Environmental Health
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2	15.52-15.59	Sagung Agung Putri Dwiastuti, Ida Ayu Dewi Kumala Ratih, IGA Ayu Dharmawati	Design of disposable dental cutting equipment in accordance with health rules in Bali Province	Oral and Dental Health
3	15.59-16.06	Septika Priskasari, Elastria Widita	Factors associated with life satisfaction among people with Edentulism in Indonesia: a data analysis from IFLS-5	Oral and Dental Health
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5	16.13-16.20	Furaida Khasanah, Chyntia Ayu Nurlita, Eldarita	Selected music has an effect on changes in a pulses just before odontectomy	Oral and Dental Health
6	16.20-16.27	Kurnia Erma Puri, Supnawadi, Baiq Mutmainnah	Relationship between feeding patterns and tooth brushing habits with dental caries in 8-10 yearsold children at Karangrejo 01 Semarang Elementary School	Oral and Dental Health
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[ABS-2]

The effectiveness between peer educators and guidance counselling teachers to reproductive health level knowledge among senior high school girls students*Niken Meilani and Nanik Setiyawati*

Poltekkes Kemenkes Yogyakarta

Abstract

Adolescents is the most vulnerable period to reproductive health problems. These problems include early pregnancy, unsafe abortion, sexuallyinfections transmitted (STIs) including the Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV), sexual abuse. Access for sex education and reproductive health services to comprehensive and youth-friendly is still very limited. There had been several studies about effective methods for increasing adolescents knowledge about reproductive health. Peer educator is a strategy of providing information that is quite effective for adolescents in increasing adolescent knowledge about adolescent reproductive health. This study aims to determine the effectiveness of peer educators and guidance and counselling teachers in adolescent reproductive health level of knowledge. The method in this study is a quantitative study with a quasi-experimental nonequivalent control group design with treatment groups using peer educators and teacher as control groups to improving reproductive health knowledge among girls students. Samples used was 70 respondents. Data collected by questionnaire that already had validity and reliability test. Data analysis used univariate, t-test and logistic regression. The results of this study showed that the provision of information was more effective through teachers with $p = 0,000$ with $\exp B = 14.5$. Need to optimizing the role of guidance and counseling teachers in providing information on adolescent reproductive health

Keywords: guidance counseling, teacher, peer, level of knowledge, adolescents

Topic: Public Health

[ABS-4]

The correlation of academic stress and academic workload with academic burnout during covid-19 pandemic among nursing students in Health Polytechnic of The Ministry of Health In Yogyakarta

Abiyyu Naufal Susanto (a), Maryana (a), Budhy Ermawan (a)*

a) Nursing Department, Health Polytechnic of the Ministry of Health in Yogyakarta
03, Tatabumi St., Banyuraden, Gamping, Sleman, D.I. Yogyakarta, Indonesia
*abiyyunaufalsusanto@gmail.com

Abstract

Background: Nursing students have the potential to experience academic stress due to the lecture system and academic demands. Clinical assignments are the main academic workload of nursing students. The Covid-19 pandemic conditions affect academic stress and academic workloads among nursing students. Stress and workload are personal factors that are predictors of burnout. Objective: To know the correlation of academic stress and academic workload with academic burnout during covid-19 pandemic among nursing students in Health Polytechnic of the Ministry of Health in Yogyakarta. Methods: This research is non-experimental study with a cross-sectional design. This research was conducted in January 2021. The population of this research were students of Nursing Department of the Health Polytechnic of the Ministry of Health in Yogyakarta. The number of samples in this research were 228 students. Pearson product moment test and multiple linear regression test were used for data analysis. Results: The results showed that there was a positive and significant correlation between academic stress and academic burnout, the amount of r was 0.641 and the p value was 0.000. There was a positive and significant correlation between academic workload and academic burnout, the amount of r was 0.677 and the p value was 0.000. The results of the significance test obtained that the F value was 98.401, the F_{table} value for α 5% = 3.04 and for α 1% was 3.88. The amount of the effective contribution of the academic stress variable was 12.44% and the effective contribution of the academic workload variable was 34.18%. The relative contribution by the academic stress variable was 26.67% while the relative contribution by the academic workload variable was 73.33%. Conclusion: There was a significant positive correlation between academic stress and academic workload with academic burnout during the Covid-19 pandemic among students in the Nursing Department of the Health Polytechnic of the Ministry of Health in Yogyakarta.

Keywords: Academic stress- Academic workload- Academic burnout- Nursing student- Covid-19 pandemic

Topic: Nursing and anesthesiology

[ABS-5]

Mixed formula of red bean flour (*Phaseolus vulgaris*) and breadfruit flour (*Artocarpus communis*) on blood lipid profile in diabetes rat induced streptozotosin-nicotinamide (STZ-NA)*Mega Nurdini, Agus Wijanarka, Almira Sitasari*

Poltekkes Kemenkes Yogyakarta

Abstract

Background: Diabetes Melitus (DM) is a chronic condition characterized by hyperglycemia. Severe and chronic DM conditions can effect fat metabolism causing dyslipidemia. This condition is characterized by an increase in total cholesterol, LDL, triglyceride levels, and a decrease in HDL levels. One of the efforts to reduce the risk of dyslipidemia in people with diabetes is to eat foods high in fiber and resistant starch, which are found in many plants, such as kidney beans and breadfruit. Processing of red beans and breadfruit into flour is also effective in increasing levels of fiber and resistant starch. Research Purposes: To determine the effect of giving a mixture formula of red bean flour and breadfruit flour on changes in blood lipid profiles in diabetic rats induced by STZ-NA. Research Methods: This study used an experimental method with pre-test and post-test control group design in the Central Laboratory for Food and Nutrition Studies (PSPG) UGM Yogyakarta. The subjects of this study were 30 Spague Dawley rats, aged 2-3 months, and weighing 150-200 g. The rats were divided into 5 groups consisting of negative control group, positive control, intervention giving red bean flour and breadfruit flour, with a dose of formula 1 (75%:25%), formula 2 (50%:50%), and formula 3 (25%:75%). Lipid profile levels were tested before and after the intervention for 21 days. The results of this study were analyzed using the One Way ANOVA test. Research Results: Based on the results of data analysis, there was a significant difference between the levels of lipid profiles (total cholesterol, LDL, HDL, and triglycerides) with the five experimental groups with p value of 0,000 ($p < 0,05$). Furthermore, the paired t test pre-test and post-test for each experimental group showed a significant difference in lipid profile levels. Conclusions: The mixed formula of red bean flour and breadfruit flour can be developed as a food alternative for DM patients who are accompanied by dyslipidemia.

Keywords: Red Bean Flour, Breadfruit Flour, Lipid Profile, Diabetic Rats**Topic:** Nutrition and Dietetic

[ABS-6]

Animation video “Anemia Rematri” and knowledge about anemia of girl adolescent*Siti Nur Annisa, Hesty Widiasih, Tri Maryani*

Poltekkes Kemenkes Yogyakarta

Abstract

Anemia is still a global health problem. The incidence of anemia among girl adolescent is still high. The results of the preliminary study found that most of the students had a low level of anemia knowledge. Elgar Dele in Arsyad stated that 30% video media is able to increase knowledge (combining audio and visual). Objective of this study to determine the effect of giving animation video “Anemia Rematri” on the level of anemia knowledge in adolescent girl. The design of this study was a quasi-experimental design with pre-test and post-test with control group design. The sample of the study were 33 students of the treatment group and 33 students of the control group. In sampling the data, the researcher used purposive sampling technique. The independent variable was the giving of the animation video. The dependent variable was the level of knowledge of anemia in girl adolescent. In collecting the data, the researcher used questionnaires. In analyzing the data, the researcher used paired sample t-test and independent sample t-test. Results showed that after the treatment in the two groups most of the students had a good level of knowledge. The paired sample t-test test in the animation video group had the p-value = 0,000 and leaflet group had the p-value = 0,000. The independent sample t-test had the p-value = 0.424. The mean in the animation video group was 17.85 higher than the mean in the leaflet group (15.94). The conclusion is that animation video “Anemia Rematri” was more effective in increasing knowledge compared to leaflet.

Keywords: Anemia- Animation Video- Knowledge- Girl Adolescent**Topic:** Midwifery

[ABS-7]

Effect of giving flour combination formula red bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L) and Breadfruit (*Artocarpus communis*) on body weight, feed intake and scfa (Short Chain Fatty Acid) levels in diabetic rats*Prita Enggar Windarti, Idi Setiyobroto, Rini Wuri Astuti*Nutrition department of Poltekkes Kemenkes Yogyakarta
Jl. Tatabumi No.3 Banyuraden, Gamping, Sleman**Abstract**

Background: Diabetes Mellitus (DM) is one of the health problems in Indonesia where the number of sufferers has increased each year. Signs and symptoms of DM sufferers are weight loss which is inversely with increase in appetite. The treatment of DM patients recognizes 4 pillars, which one is nutritional therapy. Functional foods that can be used as the implementation of nutritional therapy for DM sufferers are red beans and breadfruit. The two ingredients are combined to see the effect on changes in body weight, feed intake and SCFA level, that it illustrate the insulin sensitivity improvement of DM patients. Aim: To determine the effect of red bean and breadfruit flour combination formula giving on body weight, feed intake and SCFA level of DM rats. Method : This research used experimental methods and was carried out at Pusat Studi Pangan dan Gizi Laboratory UGM Yogyakarta, use 30 Sprague Dawley rats, aged : 2-3 months, and weigh :150-200 g. The rats were divided into 5 groups, consist : negative control, positive control, intervention of giving red bean and breadfruit flour formula, with the percentage of formula A (75%:25%), formula B (50%:50%), and formula C (25%:75%). Changes of body weight and feed intake level were observed for 21 days, while SCFA were analyzed after the intervention periode. The results were analyzed using One Way ANOVA test. Result: There was a significant difference between changes in body weight $p < 0.000$ ($p < 0.05$), the level of feed intake $p < 0.000$ ($p < 0.05$) and the total SCFA 0.014 ($p < 0.05$) in the five treatment groups. The intervention of formula giving was known have a good result to increase body weight, control appetite and increase SCFA levels compared to the control group. Conclusion: giving of combination formula of red bean flour and breadfruit flour has a significant effect in preventing polyphagia symptoms and helps in increasing body weight and SCFA levels of DM rats.

Keywords: Combination Formula of Red Bean Flour and Breadfruit Flour, Body Weight, Feed Intake Level, SCFA

Topic: Nutrition and Dietetic

[ABS-8]**The relationship of anxiety with the accuracy of the 3-month injection contraception re-visit during the Covid-19 pandemic in Sleman Regency**

Ismi Nur Aini, Yuni Kusmiyati, Nanik Setiyawati

Midwifery Department of Yogyakarta Health Polytechnic of Health Ministry

Abstract

The use of injectable contraceptives throughout Indonesia during the COVID-19 pandemic decreased from 524,989 acceptors to 341,109 acceptors with a total of 183,880 decreases. Anxiety due to the COVID-19 pandemic is one of the causes of not making a visit. The aim of this study was to know the relationship between anxiety and accuracy of 3-month injectable re-visit during the COVID-19 pandemic. This study was a cross-sectional design. The population was all old acceptor 3-month injection contraceptive who re-visited during the COVID-19 pandemic in Sleman Regency on November 2020- February 2021. The sampling technique used Consecutive with the sample used was 115 respondents. Variables in this study, which was anxiety, education, occupation, husband support, and distance to access healthy centers for Family Planning Services. Data collected using questionnaire. Chi-square and logistic regression were used in data analysis. The result in this study there was an association between anxiety and the accuracy of a 3-month re-visit of injectable birth control during the COVID-19 pandemic. After controlled variable husband support, anxiety ($p=0.000$). Inaccuracies in re-visits were 14.17 times higher in anxiety-experiencing acceptors ($OR=14.17$). There was no relationship between educational variables, husband support, and distance access to health facilities to the accuracy of re-visits ($p=0.770-0.178-0.743$). The conclusion of this study there is relationship between anxiety and accuracy of 3-month injectable re-visit during the COVID-19 pandemic. Anxiety is a risk factor toward accuracy re-visit 3-month injection contraceptive in the pandemic era of covid-19.

Keywords: COVID-19 Anxiety, Accuracy of re-visit, 3-month injectable birth control

Topic: Midwifery

[ABS-9]

The effect of health education about anticipatory guidance for breastfeeding mothers knowledge in preventing child malnutrition at working area of Puskesmas Mantrijeron Yogyakarta

Aga Rahma Putri, Atik Badi^ah, Eko Suryani

Poltekkes Kemenkes Yogyakarta

Abstract

Background : Anticipatory guidance is kind of guidance for parents which serves to educate and nurture their children according to their stage of growth and development. Mother knowledge is one of indirect factor which able to affect the occurrence of child malnutrition. Malnutrition problem that are not prevented can get worse. Objective : To know the effect of health education about anticipatory guidance for breastfeeding mothers knowledge in preventing child malnutrition at working area of Puskesmas Mantrijeron Yogyakarta. Methods : The type of this research is quasi eksperiment using pretest- posttest control group design, done on April 2021. The research's population of breastfeeding mothers who live in working area of Puskkesmas Mantrijeron Yogyakarta were 64 person and they have babies at the age of 0-24 months. Sampling technique using purposive sampling. Result : Pair t test for experiment group showed that p-value = 0,000 and pair t test for control group showed that p-value = 0,000. The results of independent t test for experiment group and control group before intervention showed p-value = 0,302 and the results for experiment group and control group after intervention showed p-value = 0,022. Conclusion : There was an effect of health education about anticipatory guidance for breastfeeding mothers knowledge in preventing child malnutrition at working area of Puskesmas Mantrijeron Yogyakarta.

Keywords: Anticipatory Guidance , Knowledge, Malnutrition

Topic: Nursing and anesthesiology

[ABS-10]

The effect of health education with SINERGIS Disc Media on the knowledge level of self-management of diabetes mellitus patients in the elderly group at the Seyegan Health Center

Joko Tigo Narimo Beki (a), Maryana, (a), Abiyyu Naufal Susanto (a), Titik Fajriyati Nur Khasanah (a), Wahyu Febriana (a)*

a) Department of Nursing, Health Polytechnic of The Ministry of Health in Yogyakarta
Tata Bumi Street 3, Gamping, Sleman, D.I Yogyakarta 55293, Indonesia

Abstract

Background: Diabetes mellitus is a disease of blood sugar, protein, and fat metabolism disorders which is often referred to as “The Silent Killer” which means it works like termites, and slowly but damages vital organs. Community empowerment needs to be done considering the tendency to increase the incidence and prevalence of diabetes mellitus around the world. **Objective:** This study aims to see the effect of the Diabetes Mellitus Integrated Monitoring System (Sistem Monitoring Terintegrasi Kensing Manis / SINERGIS) program on the level of knowledge in people with type 2 diabetes mellitus at Seyegan Health Center. **Methods:** This study used a randomized pretest-posttest control group design. The sample in this study was 40 respondents who were selected with purposive sampling technique. The research took place at the Puskesmas Seyegan Sleman, Yogyakarta Special Region. The instrument used was the DKQ-24 (Diabetes Knowledge Questionnaire) questionnaire with 24 question items. The test was a paired t test. **Result:** There is a significant difference in the mean value of knowledge between the pretest (14.21) and posttest (19.84) with a difference of 5.63 with the statistical test results of P value = 0.001 (P <0.05). **Conclusion:** From this research it can be concluded that there is an effect of health education on diabetes mellitus using Sinergis discs towards the knowledge level of diabetes mellitus patients.

Keywords: Diabetes Mellitus , Knowledge,SINERGIS Disc

Topic: Community Empowerment

[ABS-12]

The effect of website based e-poster health education on physical distancing anxiety in the Yogyakarta Ministry Of Health Polytechnic Environment*Aprilia Ega Suci Hartanti (a*), Eko Suryani (b), Julia Tri Winahyu (b), Dian Novita (b)*

Poltekkes Kemenkes Yogyakarta

Jalan Tata Bumi No. 3, Banyuraden, Gamping, Sleman, DI Yogyakarta, Republik Indonesia

Abstract

Background: In the midst of the ongoing corona virus disease outbreak, one of the policies taken by the government of the Republic of Indonesia is physical distancing with its implementation, namely work from home and learn from home. The situation in the midst of this pandemic outbreak can cause anxiety in students. This is due to frustration due to changing routines. This excessive anxiety can put a person at risk for experiencing mental emotional disorders that are at risk for mental illnesses such as depression or schizophrenia. Objective: To determine the effect of website-based e-poster health education on physical distancing anxiety in the Yogyakarta Ministry of Health Poltekkes environment. While the purpose of the research hypothesis: The hypothesis in this study is that there is an effect of website-based e-poster health education on physical distancing anxiety in the Yogyakarta Ministry of Health Polytechnic environment. Research Benefit: While practically it is expected to be able to reduce the level of anxiety regarding the application of physical distancing. Method: Quasi experiment with one group pretest-posttest design. The research sample was taken by simple random sampling. Respondents were given health education using website-based e-poster media about physical distancing. The assessment was carried out twice, namely before and after giving health education to the respondents. Result: Based on data analysis, it is known that the Asymp value. Sig. (2-tailed) of $0.000 < 0.05$, it can be concluded that the hypothesis is accepted. Thus it can be said that there is an effect of providing website-based e-poster education for pre-test and post-test. Conclusion: There is an effect of website-based e-poster health education on physical distancing anxiety in the Yogyakarta Ministry of Health Polytechnic environment

Keywords: e-poster, physical distancing, covid 19, anxiety**Topic:** Nursing and anesthesiology

[ABS-13]

An analysis of predisposition factors of coated tongue in Diponegoro National Hospital*Dini Rachmawati (a), Oedijani Santoso(b), Hesti Triwahyu Hutami(c)*

(a) Undergraduate Program, Faculty of Medicine, Diponegoro University

(b) Department of Dentistry, Faculty of Medicine, Diponegoro University

(c) Department of Internal Medicine, Faculty of Medicine, Diponegoro University

Abstract

Background: Several results of the study in Indonesia show that the age group of >45 years old has complaints of the coated tongue as the lesion with the highest percentage in the oral cavity. This occurs because the change of condition is influenced by the change of foods consumed, a decrease of saliva flow rate, and can be occurred due to the side effect of consuming antihypertensive drugs, smoking habits, and tongue brushing behavior. Objective: This study aims to find out the relationship between predisposition factors and coated tongue and find out the most contributing factors to coated tongue in the age group of >45 years old in Diponegoro National Hospital (RSND). Methods: This study used a cross-sectional design with 84 respondents of >45 years old in internal medicine polyclinic. This study was conducted by interviews of predisposition factors and TCI Shimizu for the assessment of coated tongue. The statistical test used the chi-square test and logistic regression test. Results: Respondents with a TCI value of >50% were 97.6%, and a TCI value of ≤50% were 2.4%. Chi-square test showed that there is a relationship between coated tongue and xerostomia (P=0.034), brushing the tongue (P=0.001). However, there is no relationship between coated tongue and smoking (P=1.000), consuming antihypertensive drugs (P=1.000), consuming soft food (P=0.495). The results of the logistic regression test showed that xerostomia and brushing the tongue do not affect the coated tongue partially (P=0.997). Conclusion: There is a relationship between xerostomia and brushing the tongue with coated tongue. There is no partial effect between xerostomia and brushing the tongue with coated tongue.

Keywords: Age group of >45 years old, Coated tongue, Predisposition factors.**Topic:** Oral and Dental Health

[ABS-14]

The relationship between the effect of pregnancy complaints on quality of life and the self-perception level of pregnancy**Elif Yağmur GÜR¹, Serap ÖZTÜRK ALTINAYAK²**¹Atatürk University Faculty of Health Sciences, Department of Midwifery, Erzurum, Turkey²Ondokuz Mayıs University Faculty of Health Science, Department of Midwifery, Samsun, Turkey**Abstract**

This study was conducted to evaluate the relationship between the quality of life and the level of self-perception of pregnant women. In this descriptive study, 331 pregnant women were selected by purposive sampling method between the dates February 1 and April 30, 2021. Data were collected by online survey method using the personal information form, the scale of complaints during pregnancy and their effect on quality of life and self-perception of pregnant women scale. The mean age of pregnant women and body mass index were 28.44 ± 5.95 and 25.41 ± 3.19 , respectively. It was found that 31.1% of pregnant women were at first trimester, 30.8% of them second trimester and 38.1% of them third trimester. On the other hand, 61.9% of them were multiparous and 76.7% of them were planned pregnancy. Their mean scale of complaints during pregnancy and their effect on quality of life score was 94.52 ± 30.88 . The mean maternity perception in pregnancy subscale score was 22.33 ± 4.44 and the mean body perception in pregnancy subscale score was 11.77 ± 4.01 . It was determined that there was a positive significant correlation between the mean body perception in pregnancy subscale score and the mean scale of complaints during pregnancy and their effect on quality of life score ($r=0.451$, $p<0.01$). In this study, it is concluded that pregnant women have high perceptions of maternity. Their body perceptions and levels of the quality of life at the pregnancy are moderate. As the self-perception of pregnant women has increased positively, their quality of life during pregnancy has also increased.

Keywords: Pregnancy, Self-Perception, Quality of Life**Topic:** Midwifery

[ABS-15]

The effect of bay leaf extract gel on fibroblasts in traumatic ulcers healing process

Kurnia Nisa Putri Firawan (a), Ira Anggar Kusuma (a), Hermawan-Istiadi (b), Oedijani-Santoso (a)

(a) Dentistry Study Program, Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Diponegoro
(b) Departement of Anatomical Pathology, Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Diponegoro

Abstract

Traumatic ulcers are common lesion in the oral cavity. The healing process of traumatic ulcers consists of 4 phases, namely hemostasis, inflammation, proliferation, and remodeling phases. Fibroblast cells have an important role in wound healing process which appears on the 3rd day and reaches its peak on the 7th day after injury. Bay leaves contain compounds that have anti-inflammatory pharmacological. The research aims to determine the effect of bay leaf extract gel on fibroblasts cells in accelerating the ulcers healing process. The type of research is experimental research using post-test only control group design which consists of control group, treatment groups were given 5 percent and 10 percent of bay leaf extract gel with 5 samples of male Wistar rats on each group. The gel was applied twice a day until the 5th day. Labial mucosa in rats was observed using Hematoxylin Eosin staining to see fibroblast cells. Data analysis used one way Anova test and Post Hoc LSD test. The results show that the 10 percent of bay leaf extract gel treatment group is higher than the control group and the 5 percent of bay leaf extract gel treatment group with a significant difference. The conclusion of this study is that bay leaf extract gel can increase of fibroblast cells in accelerating the ulcers healing process.

Keywords: bay leaf extract, traumatic ulcer, wound healing, fibroblast cell

Topic: Oral and Dental Health

[ABS-16]

The effectiveness of handwashing education with audiovisual methods to increase students' knowledge and attitudes about handwashing at Smu Negeri 1 Gamping, Sleman Yogyakarta*Kusbaryanto and Sari*

Faculty of medicine and health Universitas Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta

Abstract

Background: Hand hygiene plays a crucial role in preventing infection in patients and health workers. Hand washing is the most effective action in hand hygiene, because it can prevent cross-transmission of microorganisms and reduce the incidence of nosocomial infections. The purpose of this study was to analyze the effectiveness of hand washing education with audiovisual methods to increase students' knowledge and attitudes about hand washing at SMA NEGERI 1 Gamping, Yogyakarta. Method: The design of this research is a quantitative research using a Quasi-experimental design with One group Pretest and Posttest Design. This is a type of analytical research. There is one research group where a comparison has been made before and after being given an intervention or treatment in the form of education with audiovisuals. Data collection was done by questionnaire- the number of samples was 107. Results: The results of measuring knowledge about handwashing before and after education were carried out with the Wilcoxon test, obtained $p = 0.001$. This shows that there is a difference in knowledge between before and after education. The results of measuring attitudes about hand washing before and after education were carried out with the Wilcoxon test, obtained $p = 0.001$. This shows that there is a significant difference between before and after education. Conclusions: Education about hand washing with audiovisual methods significantly increases knowledge and attitudes about handwashing in Gamping high school students in Yogyakarta.

Keywords: Keywords: education - handwashing - knowledge – attitude**Topic:** Public Health

[ABS-17]

Mapping of DHF in Sleman Regency in 2015-2019 based on some indicators*Rizqi Intan Wahyuni (a*), Agus Kharmayana Rubaya (b), Yamtana (b)*

- a) Department of Environmental Health Poltekkes Kemenkes Yogyakarta
*rizqiintanwhy@gmail.com
- b) Department of Environmental Health Poltekkes Kemenkes Yogyakarta

Abstract

DHF is an endemic disease in Sleman Regency. Kapanewon or District in Sleman Regency has not reached national target (IR 49 per population). Geographic Information System (GIS)-based mapping hopefully can help produce the right policies in controlling DHF cases in Sleman Regency. This research aims to descriptively understand the distribution of DHF cases related to Larvae-free Index, Healthy Houses, Clean and Healthy Life Behavior in the household, and population density in Sleman Regency in 2015-2019 with GIS-based mapping. This descriptive research used Ecological Study design with retrospective approach, through GIS-based mapping in overlays form. It used total sampling of 17 Kapanewon in Sleman Regency. Variables used are secondary data for 2015-2019 obtained from Health Department and Civil Registry Department of Sleman Regency. DHF incidence in Sleman Regency for 5 years (2015-2019) has fluctuated and tends to occur a lot in Kapanewon which close to Yogyakarta City, Bantul Regency, and Kulon Progo Regency. Map overlay shows Larvae-free Index and population density related to DHF cases. Healthy Houses and Clean and Healthy Life Behavior in the household not related to DHF cases in Sleman Regency. Chi-square test shows that population density related to DHF cases. Meanwhile, Larvae-free Index, Healthy Houses, and Clean and Healthy Life Behavior in the household not related to DHF cases in Sleman Regency. Based on descriptive analysis, Larvae-free Index and population density related to DHF cases in Sleman Regency. Based on Chi-square test, population density related to DHF cases in Sleman Regency in 2015-2019.

Keywords: DHF mapping- factors related to DHF- map overlay

Topic: Environmental Health

[ABS-18]

The influence of giving health education with the smart link application to increase knowledge of first aid in students of 1st state Senior High School of Godean*Titik Fajriyati Nur K(a*) Maryana (b) R.R Sri Arini W (c)*

Yogyakarta Ministry Health Polytechnic Student Department of Nursing

Abstract

Background: Health education of First Aid is essential to learn senior high school students, due to the high number of emergencies at that age. Health education of First Aid is an option to lessen the number of emergencies. Objective : To identify the influence of health education with the Smart Link application to increase the level of first aid knowledge high school students. Methods: This research is a Quasi-experimental design with a randomized pre-test post-test control group design. The sample in this research was 60 respondents with the purposive sampling technique. The independent variable in this study was health education with Smart Link and the dependent in this research was first aid knowledge for students. Data were collected using a first aid questionnaire and statistical tests were carried out using the Independent T-Test and T-paired Test with a significance value of $p = 0.05$. Research Results: There is an effect after given health education with the Smart Link application on the level of first aid knowledge in high school students with a value of $p = 0.004$. This study shows that health education with the Smart Link application has an influence on the level of first aid knowledge. Conclusion: There is an effect of health education with the Smart Link application on the level of first aid knowledge senior high schools student.

Keywords: Smart Link, First Aid, Health Education, High School Students**Topic:** Nursing and anesthesiology

[ABS-19]

Social media line as a health promotion media of adolescents oral hygiene*Dientyah Nur Anggina (a*), Putri Erlyn (a)*

a) Faculty of Medicine University of Muhammadiyah Palembang

* drg.dientdita@gmail.com

Abstract

Problems related to adolescent's oral hygiene are generally due to lack of information, understanding and awareness to maintain good oral hygiene. Riset Kesehatan Dasar results in 2018 showed 55.6% of adolescents aged 10-14 years and 51.9% of adolescents aged 15-19 years suffered from oral health diseases. The majority of social media users in Indonesia are adolescent, the provision of health information through social media Line can be used as a promotion media of adolescent's oral hygiene. To determine the effectiveness of social media ^Line^ for promoting adolescents^ oral hygiene. This quasi experimental research, using the intervention group and the control group (nonequivalent control group design). The research sample were students of SMP IT Al Furqon Palembang many as 46 students. Instruments used in the form of a questionnaire and OHI-S index. Analysis data was processed using Wilcoxon test and Independent t-test. Wilcoxon test showed there were differences in the improvement of knowledge level ($p=0.007$) and OHI-S index ($p=0.005$) before and after intervention using social media Line. Independent t-test showed there were differences in the improvement of knowledge level ($p=0.001$) and OHI-S index ($p=0.001$) between the intervention group and the control group. So it can be concluded that there were the effect of social media Line as a health promotion media in the improvement of knowledge level and OHI-S index in adolescent.

Keywords: health promotion media- adolescent oral hygiene- social media**Topic:** Oral and Dental Health

[ABS-20]

The differences of hand washing with soap level knowledge before and after receiving health promotion about hand washing with soap in students at Pusri Junior High School*Resy Asmalia (a*), Thia Prameswarie (b), Chairunissa Alya Ananda (c)*

a & b) Department of Public Health and Family Medicine, Faculty of Medicine University of Muhammadiyah Palembang

* asmaliareisy351@gmail.com

c) Medical Study Program, Faculty of Medicine University of Muhammadiyah Palembang

Abstract

Healthy and clean lifestyle (PHBS) still become specific attention for the government. One of PHBS indicators is washing hands with soap (HWWS). HWWS is a simple technique and beneficial to prevent various diseases, that can be prevented by washing our hands correctly, such as diarrhea and acute respiratory infection (ARI). The level of washing hands habit and knowledge of the society in Indonesia is still low and there are 17% of school age children who wash their hand with clean water and soap. The objective of this study is to identify the difference of hand washing with soap (HWWS) knowledge level before and after receiving health promotion about hand washing with soap (HWWS) on male and female students at PUSRI Junior High School. The sample was taken by using total sampling technique and there were 90 samples that meet the inclusive and exclusive criteria. From the result of this study showed there is a difference on washing hands with soap (HWWS) knowledge level before and after receiving health promotion about hand washing with soap (HWWS) on male and female students at PUSRI Junior High School with p-value (0,000). It can be concluded that there is a difference of hand washing with soap (HWWS) knowledge level before and after receiving health promotion about hand washing with soap (HWWS) on male and female students at PUSRI Junior High School.

Keywords: PHBS- Hand washing with soap- habits

Topic: Community Empowerment

[ABS-21]

Healthy drink soya zalacca (Soca) rich in Iron and Vitamin C as a drink for pregnant women*Ira Muslina 1*, Nur Cahya Rachmawati 2, Zulya Erda 3, Nurul Aini Suria Saputri 4*

1,2,4 Department of Midwifery Poltekkes Kemenkes Tanjungpinang, Indonesia

3 Department of Environmental Health Poltekkes Kemenkes Tanjungpinang, Indonesia

Abstract

Many people in Riau Islands do not eat vegetables, causing many of them to suffer from anemia. The high number of marine resources such as fish and shellfish has made Riau Island people forget the importance of consuming these fruits and vegetables. Pregnant women in Kepri Province have the habit of consuming certain drinks every day, namely soya/tofu water. Tofu water is a processed drink made from soybeans that are high in iron. This research aimed to make SOCA healthy drinks for pregnant women. This research was conducted in July-August 2020, in the Integrated Chemistry Laboratory of the Poltekkes Kemenkes Tanjungpinang with panelists from the Poltekkes Kemenkes Tanjungpinang students. The result is the best formulation from the organoleptic test on students were tested on pregnant women who live around the Poltekkes Kemenkes Tanjungpinang environment. Then the preference test is carried out to determine which flavor is the best. This product is made in 3 stages, namely, separating the essence of Salak Sari Intan, combining tofu water and Salak Sari Intan essence, and testing the preference for the product. The distinctive aroma of tofu water and Salak Sari Intan essence is mixed in this SOCA drink. It makes the aroma of this drink its characteristic. The panelists also like the color of the solution because the resulting color looks brighter than other solutions. SOCA drink is a very suitable drink as an alternative to prevent anemia.

Keywords: SOCA- soya- salacca zalacca- iron- pregnant women**Topic:** Nutrition and Dietetic

[ABS-22]

Model of reproductive health development in adolescents with special needs: intellectual disabilities based on teacher need assessment in Yogyakarta*Barkah Wulandari1*, Apri Nur Wulandari2*

1. Lecturer at STIKES Notokusumo Yogyakarta
2. Lecturer at STIKES Notokusumo Yogyakarta

Abstract

Adolescents with intellectual disabilities are teenagers who have a low level of intelligence compared to adolescents of their age. This situation causes adolescents with intellectual disabilities have an inability to adapt a developmental behavior. It happens because they have the same biological development as adolescents of their age, thus often causing various problems related to reproduction. This condition because many teachers who have not received information about reproductive health, consider it taboo, especially for the topic of sexuality and the limitations of children's abilities. So, the teacher's role is limited to reminding or helping young girls to change pads when menstruating, helping and reminding them how to clean themselves after urinate or defecate. The research focus on the needs of teachers related to reproductive health based on need assessment in adolescents with intellectual disabilities. This research was conducted with a qualitative research approach with the Focus Group Discussion (FGD) Teacher. The study population was a teacher in SLB Negeri 2 Yogyakarta. There are 4 themes based on this study, namely: Adolescents with intellectual disabilities are feeling the need for sexuality, School Efforts in controlling sexual abuse of adolescents with intellectual disabilities in schools, Efforts to increase teacher capabilities is by providing reproductive health material, Need assessment of teacher needs for adolescents with intellectual disabilities reproductive health. This research have new result about teacher needs for reproductive health based on teacher needs assessment which is: Reproductive health curriculum, teaching instruments, parental participation for the sustainability of reproductive health materials at home. Reproductive health curriculum-related material in each age stage.

Keywords: adolescent- intellectual disabilities- reproductive health

Topic: Nursing and anesthesiology

[ABS-24]

Occupational lung function impairment by particulate matter 2,5 (PM_{2,5}) exposure in fish smoking workers*Purnama Sidebang (1*)*

(1) Jurusan Kesehatan Lingkungan Poltekkes Kemenkes Ternate,
Jln. Cempaka RT.015 RW 05 No 794 Ternate Selatan, Maluku Utara, Indonesia.
*purthebank88@gmail.com

Abstract

As a coastal City, Ternate has smoked fish products that are traditionally managed by burning using firewood or coconut shells, resulting in air pollution pollutants, like fine particulate matter (PM_{2,5}), an air pollutants which are harmful to the health of fish smoking workers, such as pulmonary function impairment. This study aims to determine the effect of PM_{2,5} exposure on lung function impairment of fish smoking workers in Ternate City. It was a cross-sectional study design, purposive sampling technique of 15 people from a total of 12 smoking houses. The median of PM_{2,5} concentration in fish smoking houses was 440.15µg/m³ and about 86% of workers had been exposed to PM_{2,5} exceeded the nationally required daily quality standard, 53.3% of respondents had lung function impairment based on FEV₁ / FVC lung capacity measurements, from the statistical analysis results obtained $p = 1$, meaning that there was no difference pulmonary function impairment in workers with PM_{2,5} exposure that exceeds the quality standard and does not exceed the quality standard. OR 1.167 was obtained, meaning that workers exposed to PM_{2,5} > quality standards have odds 1.167 times higher to have lung function impairment than workers exposed to PM_{2,5} ≤ quality standards. Exposure to PM_{2,5} that exceeds the quality standard will increase the risk of having lung function impairment in fish smoking workers in Ternate City.

Keywords: PM_{2.5}- lung function impairment- smoked fish- workers- air pollution

Topic: Environmental Health

[ABS-25]

Perceptions and barriers of medical personnel in the application of clinical pathways: literature review*Hana Muhammad(a*), Ariyanti Saleh(b), Rini Rachmawaty(b)*

a) Master of Nursing Program, Faculty of Nursing, Hasanuddin University, South Sulawesi, Indonesia

b) Department of Nursing, Faculty of Nursing, Hasanuddin University, South Sulawesi, Indonesia

Abstract

Background: Clinical Pathway can provide consistent, safe, efficient, effective, and timely care that will result in positive outcomes for patients and reduce the inappropriate use of unnecessary resources. Purpose: to identify staff perceptions and barriers of medical personnel in the application of clinical pathways. Method: literature review with search for articles through PubMed, Wiley, ProQUEST, and Google Scholar databases. Screening is carried out using the last 10 years from 2010 to 2020, relevant to the title of the study and in full text form and in accordance with the research objectives. Result: The application of clinical pathways is perceived as a process that is directed at realizing benefits, creating habits and requiring enthusiasm, support, and time. Clinical pathways are important to control actions for quality control and cost control so as to provide optimal results for patients. while the barriers for medical personnel that often arise in the application of clinical pathways include not having sufficient time, lack of direction and guidance related to clinical pathways, lack of staff awareness of the importance of clinical pathways, lack of compliance in documentation and lack of staff commitment in implementing clinical pathways. Conclusion: the implementation of an Integrated clinical pathway that involves multidisciplinary health service providers requires good commitment and cooperation to produce quality health services.

Keywords: Perception- Barriers- Integrated Clinical Pathways.

Topic: Nursing and anesthesiology

[ABS-26]

Knowledge, attitude, and practice of dengue in Bandung City: Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) Techniques using SmartPLS*Hubullah Fuadzy (1), Heni Prasetyowati (1)*

(1) Unit of Health Research and Development of Pangandaran

Abstract

So many health promotion programmes in order to increase public awareness, yet dengue fever cases are still increasing every year. This matter is related to poor understanding and low level of adherence in dengue vector control efforts in many societal groups mainly in Bandung City. This study presents PLS-SEM technique in addressing the relationship path between variables of knowledge, attitude, practice, and the presence of mosquitoes. The data were obtained from structured interviews to 783 respondents in Bandung City in 2016. SmartPLS software v.3 was used to model the variables under study. The model shows that knowledge had a positive and a significant on attitude (path coefficient = 0.167- P = 0.000- R2 = 0.028), and practice (path coefficient = 0.120- P = 0.014- R2 = 0.029). Attitude had a positive and a significant on practice (path coefficient = 0.105- P = 0.036- R2 = 0.029). However, practice had insignificant on the presence of mosquitoes (P = 0.378). This study revealed that knowledge is able to increase awareness to conduct practice, but the practice are still incorrectly conducted, therefore dengue vector mosquitoes control is still poorly. Our study recommended to evaluate the implementation of government programs, especially dengue vector control on Covid-19 pandemic period.

Keywords: Dengue- knowledge- attitude- practice- vector control**Topic:** Public Health

[ABS-28]

The quality of compost using skipjack gill with anaerob method*Dwi Wahyu Purwiningsih, Sakriani*

POLTEKKES KEMENKES TERNATE

Abstract

Anaerobic composting is a composting process that requires oxygen availability. Oxygen is needed by microorganisms to remodel organic material during the composting process. Anaerobic composting is a composting process that does not require the availability of oxygen, but only requires the heat from outside. Skipjack fish (*Katsuwonus pelamis*) is a medium-sized fish from the family *Skombridae* (tuna), the only species of the genus *Katsuwonus*. Body length of the largest Skipjack could reach 1 meter and the weight more than 18 kg. The back part is purplish to dark blue and lower abdomen is silver belly and equipped with 4 to 6 black stripes extending to the side of the body. Dcales can only be found on the body scars or coreset and lateral line. Inner and outer part of fish waste from processing were potential to be processed into fertilizer/compost. Generally, fish waste contains many nutrients, namely N (Nitrogen), P (Posforus), and K (Potassium). The purpose of this study was to determine the quality of compost, composting time and number of composts with the addition of skipjack gills. This was an experimental research. In the process of composting the amount of vegetable waste used as much as 40 kg, and skipjack gill about 2 kg. The results of this study showed that the compost produced by the addition skipjack gills for 24 days was 2.7 Kg. While, control group, composting for 24 days produced compost about 2.4 kg. Physically, the color of compost-based skipjack gills was blackish brown, smells of fish gills and has a fine texture like soil. A bit different with compost from control group, the color was light brown, smelling of soil and has a fine texture like soil. It is recommended to further researchers to conduct research by utilizing Skipjack Fish Gills with different composting methods.

Keywords: Compost, skipjack's gill, anaerob**Topic:** Environmental Health

[ABS-29]

Utilization of the maternal child health book to maternal knowledge during the COVID 19 pandemic*Melly Damayanti(a)*, Maysarah(a)*

a) Poltekkes Kemenkes Tanjungpinang
Jurusan Kebidanan Poltekkes Kemenkes Tanjungpinang,
Jln. Arief Rahman Hakim No 1, Tanjungpinang, Indonesia.

*Email: apriyandimelly@gmail.com

Abstract

Early 2020, there was a pandemic of COVID 19 infection that can affect anyone. This pandemic affects the health status of mothers and children. To prevent the spread of COVID 19, almost all routine services, including maternal and newborn health services. The contribution of health workers is very important during this pandemic, especially the independence of mothers in maintaining their health. One solution is to increase the use of Maternal and Child Health Books (KIA) by mothers. The MCH handbook is one of the most useful recording, educational and communication media during this pandemic. Mothers and families are expected to independently use the MCH Handbook to increase knowledge and health status. The purpose of this study was to analyze the relationship between the function of the MCH book and the mother's knowledge about MCH. This study was conducted in May until July 2020 in Tanjungpinang City. This study was used a crosssectional design. The population of this study was all pregnant women in the third trimester. Samples were taken of 40 people conducted by purposive sampling technique. Univariate analysis of the data for the frequency distribution test, bivariate chi squared test. The results of the study were that there are relationships between the function of recording the MCH book and the function of communicating the MCH Book with knowledge of pregnant women. There is no relationship between the education function of the MCH Handbook with knowledge of pregnant women

Keywords: maternal child health book, maternal knowledge, COVID 19

Topic: Midwifery

[ABS-30]

The use of seated grinder reduces complaints of musculoskeletal disorders, workload, and increases work productivity of Pandai Besi in Gubug Village, Tabanan-Bali*Ida Ayu Made Sri Arjani, Cok Dewi Widhya Hana Sundari, IGA Dhyana Putri, Ni Nengah Ariati*

Polytechnic of Health Denpasar

Abstract

Background: Pandai Besi is one of the small industries that is developing in Gubug Village, Tabanan Regency. One of the processes is making household tools, the workers will be faced with tools in the form of grinders. In this process, the worker holds a vibrating grinder weighing more than 1.5 kg, and sits on the floor. Working with an unergonomic attitude, being exposed to vibration for a long time is an additional burden that will cause musculoskeletal complaints, Raynauds Syndrome, Tenosynovitis, and Carpal Tunnel Syndrome in workers. The purpose of this study was to determine The Use Seated Grinder to Reduce Complaints of Musculoskeletal disorders, Workload, and Increase Work Productivity of Pandai Besi in Gubug Village, Tabanan. Methods: This research is an experimental study with treatment by subject design. The selection of simple random sampling with a table of random numbers, with sample size is 16 people. Descriptive data includes age, weight, height, and body mass index. Normality test was carried out on musculoskeletal complaints data, workload data, and work productivity data. If normally distributed parametric statistical tests paired samples t-test difference test at significance level is 0.05, and if not, non-parametric statistical tests were performed, Wilcoxon's difference test at significance level is 0.05. Results: The mean age of the subjects was 49.112 years, body weight was 66.68, height was 162.31 cm and the subject body mass index was 25.29 kgm². There was a decrease in musculoskeletal complaints by 13.2 percent, a decrease in workload by 12.7 percent, an increase in productivity by 50.14 percent. Conclusion: There was a significant decrease between musculoskeletal complaints, workload, before and after the use of a seated grinder $p < 0.05$, there was a significant increase between work productivity before and after the use of a seated grinder.

Keywords: Seated Grinder, Musculoskeletal Complaints, Workload, Work Productivity**Topic:** Environmental Health

[ABS-31]

The challenges of improving sanitation in a community based intervention: study in Podok Village, South Kalimantan*Syarifah Nuraini (a), Sri Handayani (a), Paisal (a), Suharmiati (a)*

National Institute of Health Research and Development

Abstract

The use of floating latrines in communities in river areas is still an environmental health problem in South Kalimantan today. To improve people's behaviour in defecating, various efforts can be made with different approaches. This study aims to obtain a model of change in defecation behaviour by using community empowerment and participatory action research approach. The intervention process consists of planning the establishment of sanitation entrepreneurs, training for skilled workers in the community to build latrines, and changing agents to increase knowledge and awareness of the community. The results showed a change in the knowledge and attitudes of change agents and the community in sanitation behaviour. However, changes in the act of defecating are difficult to change because to make healthy latrines requires money- meanwhile, the need for healthy latrines is still not a priority for people with low economies. Therefore, sanitation entrepreneurs must operate as community capital to have healthy latrines.

Keywords: sanitation, community-based intervention, healthy latrines**Topic:** Environmental Health

[ABS-32]

Empowerment of family in giving massage therapy reduce complaints of acute respiratory tract infection in children*Ni Luh Kompyang Sulisnadewi (a*), I Ketut Labir (a), Suratiah (a)*

a) Nursing Departement Politehcnic of Health Denpasar
Pulau Moyo Street No 33 Denpasar
*sulisnadewi337@gmail.com

Abstract

Acute Respiratory Tract Infection (ARI) is a disease that often occurs in children. ARI is one of the main causes of patient visits at the public health (40%-60%) and hospitals (15%-30%). One of the complementary therapies that can be used to treat ARI complaints in children is massage therapy or massage therapy. techniques Massage therapy for the common cold can facilitate the release of secrets, make the child feel more comfortable, and increase the child's sense of comfort. This study aims to determine the effectiveness of family empowerment in providing massage therapy to changes in ARI complaints in toddlers. The design of this study used an approach experimental with a two-group pre-post-test design. The population in this study were children under five who suffered from ARI in the working area of the Denpasar Selatan IV Public Health Center. The sample was taken using a purposive sampling technique with a planned sample size of 30 people for each group. Analysis of the data using the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test and the Mann Whitney test. The symptom change graph was used to show the time of disappearance of ARI symptoms in both groups. The results showed that giving therapy as a complementary therapy by the family gave a good effect on complaints of colds in infants with ARI, but no statistically significant effect was found on cough complaints. Giving massage therapy is recommended to always be done by parents in children who have ARI to accelerate healing

Keywords: Massage therapy -Acute Respiratory Tract Infection -Family empowerment

Topic: Nursing and anesthesiology

[ABS-33]

NERD APPS : an anesthetic pharmacology learning media based application for anesthetist student during the Covid-19 Pandemic

Maulina Galuh Arifah, Bondan Palestin, Pramadita Elena, Juwita Putri Kartini, Doni Setiawan
Department of Nursing Poltekkes Kemenkes Yogyakarta, Indonesia

Abstract

Background : The COVID-19 pandemic significantly impacts learning process especially among anesthetist student. Most of them may experience difficulty on memorizing a lot of anesthetic drugs and its use. Due to restrictions and social distancing during pandemic, they are not able to have an offline classes that might require them to look at the real anesthetic drugs, so this nerd apps is created in order to facilitate anesthetist student to memorizing anesthetic drugs, visualize, and also understand when its use. Objective : This study aimed to determine the effect of nerd apps on improving anesthetic drugs memory among anesthetist student during the covid-19 pandemic in Health Polytecnic Yogyakarta indonesia. Methods : This development study of NERD APPS is using the 4D model consisting of Define, Design, Develop and Disseminate. This will be a quasi-experimental study with pretest/posttest design to test the effectiveness of this application on improving memories. Thirty students in fifth semester of nursing anesthesiology was selected using convenience sampling. Results : Expected there will be a significant effect of nerd on improving memory. Conclusion : Nerd apps is expected proven effective in improving anesthetic drugs memory. Therefore, this study offers a new and innovative app that fits with the covid-19 outbreak situation to help anesthetist nursing student remember name of anesthetic drugs and its use easily. The findings also support mnemonic method as a part of memorizing.

Keywords: COVID-19- Anesthetist Nursing Student - Learning Media- Application

Topic: Nursing and anesthesiology

[ABS-34]

Implementation of tb active case finding by puskesmas officers on the achievements of new tb case findings at DIY*Sri Arini Winarti Rinawati, Wahyu Ratna, Induniasih*

Poltekkes Kemenkes Yogyakarta

Abstract

Background: Tuberculosis (TB) is a problem in developing countries because the rate of disease incidence is still high and is the 10th leading cause of death in the world. As TB prevalence cases increase, community participation in finding new TB cases is increasingly important. The method used by various countries is by community-based case finding or active case finding in the community (active case finding). Objective: Evaluating the implementation of the program in the discovery of new TB cases by TB officers at the health center in an effort to control TB in DIY Method: This type of research is a basic survey. Subjects of Puskesmas staff in Yogyakarta are 121 people. The sampling technique was random sampling. The instrument used was a questionnaire containing knowledge, behavior, and types of activities. The analysis uses frequency distribution and is presented in tabular form. Result: Puskesmas DIY staff have taken several steps in carrying out new TB case finding in the community, such as Active Case Finding, Pasive Case Finding, knock on doors, counseling, screening and screening. The level of knowledge of puskesmas officers related to the implementation of Active Case Finding is sufficient. There are obstacles in the implementation of new TB case finding, among others, time and lack of personnel, budgetary factors, and some areas that do not yet have cadres. Conclusion: Implementation of the discovery of new TB cases in DIY has not been reached to the maximum.

Keywords: active case finding, community health centers, Tuberculosis**Topic:** Nursing and anesthesiology

[ABS-35]

Path analysis: risk factors for asphyxia neonatorum*Heni Puji W, Diani Fadmi Putri*

Poltekkes Kemenkes Yogyakarta

Abstract

Background: An important indicator in determining the level of public health can be monitored from the infant mortality rate. According to a report from the World Health Organization (WHO), every year approximately 3% (3.6 million) of the 120 million newborns experience neonatal jaundice and nearly 1 million of these babies later die. Jaundice in newborns occurs in 50%-60% of all infants in the first week of life. The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of risk factors for the incidence of asphyxia neonatorum in children. Method: This study used a case control design with simple random sampling. The research subjects were infants aged 0-28 days in the Bantul region in 2019 totaling 114 respondents with a 1:1 ratio of 57 cases and 57 controls. Collecting data using primary data with a questionnaire (google form). The analysis used chi-square, logistic regression, and path analysis. Result: Based on the results of the multivariate analysis, the type of labor at high risk for the incidence of jaundice with an OR of 4,169. The results of the path analysis showed that the biggest factor influencing the incidence of neonatal jaundice was diabetes mellitus ($b = 0.341$ - $SE = 0.056$ - $p = 0.004$). Conclusion: Variables that have a direct relationship are gestational age, type of delivery, birth weight of the baby, breast milk and diabetes mellitus. While the variables that have an indirect relationship are blood type and trauma.

Keywords: neonatal jaundice, path analysis, risk factors

Topic: Midwifery

[ABS-36]

Speos method (stimulation of endorphin massage, oxytocin massage, and suggestive) activates let down reflex (ldr) of postpartum mother at Public Health Center Of Denpasar

Ni Wayan Armini, Gusti Ayu Marhaeni, I Gusti Ayu Surati, Ni Made Dwi Mahayati, Ni Wayan Suarniti, Ni Komang Erny Astiti, Ni Luh Putu Sri Erawati
Midwifery Department, Health of Polytechnic of Denpasar, Bali, Indonesia

Abstract

Background: Breast milk is the most important food, especially in the first months of a baby's life. The best nutrition on the first day of a baby's life is colostrum. Delayed and insufficient milk production can cause mothers not to give breast milk to their babies. The process of releasing milk also depends on the Let-Down Reflex (LDR). One way to facilitate breast milk production is to apply the Stimulation of Endorphin Massage, Oxytocin Massage, and Suggestive (SPEOS) method. The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of the SPEOS Method on the Let-Down Reflex (LDR) Activation in Postpartum.

Methods: The study design used a pre-experimental one-group pre-test - post-test. The location of the study was conducted at public health of Denpasar that received delivery services. The research period is May to October 2019. The population is postpartum who were treated at public health care of Denpasar and fulfilled the specified inclusion criteria. The data collection instrument used a questionnaire. Statistical analysis with Wilcoxon test.

Results: The result found the median of LDR of postpartum before SPEOS method (2 with a range of 1-3) and after SPEOS method (5 with a range 4-6) indicated an increase in the LDR score (p-value < 0,001).

Conclusion: The conclusion is that the SPEOS method increases the activation of Let Down Reflexes (LDR) in postpartum. Suggestion to public health centers and to health workers to compile and set operational standards for SPEOS procedures and implement this method for each postpartum mother.

Keywords: oxytocin, endorphins, massage, suggestive, let-down reflex, postpartum

Topic: Midwifery

[ABS-37]

Development of BCD-Based Health Promotion Model (Benefit, Comparative and Dangerous) Improving Adolescent Resilience to Exposure to Unhealthy Food Advertisements*I Putu Suiraoaka (a*), Ni Komang Wiardani (a), Indhira Shagti (b)*

a) Nutrition Departement, Poltekkes Kemenkes Denpasar

* suiraoaka@gmail.com

b) Nutrition Departement, Poltekkes Kemenkes Kupang

Abstract

Lifestyle is a person's pattern in the world which is expressed in his activities, interests, and opinions. Therefore, advertising can also influence the way people are not only a necessity but as a way of life. Changes in behavior occur more quickly when the person concerned feels the benefits (benefits), can compare the information obtained from the information received, and knows the dangers (dangerous) of their behavioral choices. The general objective of this study was to determine the effectiveness of the BCD-based health promotion model (Benefit, Comparative and Dangerous) to increase adolescent resilience to exposure to unhealthy food advertisements. This study is a quasi-experimental study with a randomized pretest and posttest control group design. The research was conducted in Denpasar City and Kupang City. The reason for taking these two locations is because of the differences in the lifestyle of teenagers in the two places. Where in the city of Denpasar due to the impact of tourism there was a rapid and massive cultural shock, while in the city of Kupang this did not happen. The population in this study were high school teenagers who live in the cities of Denpasar and Kupang with a total sample of 100 in each city. Samples were taken by using the Multistage Random Sampling technique. Data were collected by interview method using a questionnaire. The results showed: the design of a BCD-based health promotion model (Benefit, Comparative and Dangerous) was carried out with an offline approach (advocacy and education to schools) and online (with Instagram and FB media) with the tagline 'let's eat healthily'. The application of the BCD (Benefit, Comparative and Dangerous) model is effective in increasing the resilience of adolescents to exposure to unhealthy food advertisements.

Keywords: resilience, adolescents, behavior change**Topic:** Public Health

[ABS-38]

The level of anxiety of senior high school adolescents during the Covid-19 pandemic*Nyoman Ribek (1), Ni Luh Putri Kristina Mellani (2), N.L.P Yunianti S.C (3)*

Polkesden = Poltekkes Kemenkes Denpasar
Jl. P.Moyo N.33 Denpasar Bali Indonesia

Abstract

In the era of the covid -19 pandemic in 2019-2020, high school teenagers must be able to adapt in dealing with challenging educational situations. This adaptability is very important to prevent anxiety because high school teenagers are still unstable in dealing with unexpected conditions where school closures are carried out, distance learning, just staying at home, unable to go with peers to relieve fatigue. Anxiety can also occur due to lack of information about the condition of the pandemic, news that is too excited in the mass media. The purpose of this study was to determine the level of anxiety of high school teenagers during the Covid-19 pandemic. This study uses a quantitative descriptive approach. The number of samples in this study were 314 students of SMA Negeri 8 Denpasar Bali using the Simple Random Sampling Technique. The measuring instrument used is the HAM-A (Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale) questionnaire. The results showed that from 314 respondents, the average score was not anxious, most of the respondents were in the not anxious category as many as 152 respondents (48.4%), experienced mild anxiety as many as 126 respondents (40.1%), moderate anxiety as many as 30 respondents. (9.6%), 6 respondents (1.9%), severe anxiety and no respondent experienced panic. It was concluded that most high school teenagers did not experience anxiety, a small portion also experienced mild, moderate to severe anxiety. It is recommended that high school teenagers be able to manage their anxiety well during the Covid 19 pandemic by getting enough rest, relaxing and complying with health protocols.

Keywords: Covid-19, Anxiety Levels, Senior High School Adolescents

Topic: Nursing and anesthesiology

[ABS-39]

Design Of Disposable Dental Cutting Equipment In Accordance With Health Rules In Bali Province*Sagung Agung Putri Dwiastuti (a*), Ida Ayu Dewi Kumala Ratih(b), IGA Ayu Dharmawati (c)*

a) Dental Hygienest Departement, Polytechnic of Health Ministry of Health Denpasar
Jalan Pulau Moyo no 33, Denpasar 80222, Indonesia

*JurKesGigidenpasar@gmail.com

b) Medical Laboratory Technology Depastement
Jalan Sanitasi no1, Denpasar Selatan 80224, Indonesia

Abstract

Tooth-cutting is a ceremony that must be carried out by Hindus in Bali. The tradition of the Tooth-cutting Ceremony contains a deep meaning for life. Tooth-cutting ceremonies in Bali vary widely, and teeth are often cut in bulk, so it is feared that disease transmission will occur. The purpose of this study was to design a disposable dental cutter in the province of Bali. The research was carried out with a transformative mixed methods design, namely the researcher used qualitative and quantitative tests. The qualitative test used semi-structured interviews with the Delphi method to 7 experts and 15 sangging practitioners to obtain disposable dental cutting tools according to health rules. After getting an agreement on the disposable tooth cutter, a seminar and hands on was held for the sangging to obtain quantitative data through the Post-test only control design test. The results of the qualitative research using the Delphi method showed that the experts agreed that the new tooth cutting tool was designed to be a disposable device, because this tool did not affect or conflict with the tooth-cutting process. The results of quantitative research on the sangging can accept a disposable appliance designed according to health rules, as evidenced by the Wilcoxon signed Ranks test, the perception of sangging of a disposable tooth cutter with a p value <0.05.

Keywords: sangging, disposable tools, disease transmission

Topic: Oral and Dental Health

[ABS-40]

Literature Review : The Effectiveness of The Sexual Orientation Change Effort (Soce) Methode for Egodistonic Homosexuality

*Tenang Aristina**, *Nunung Rachmawati*, *Yayang Harigustian*, *Mahar Agusno*³,
*Qoryamiradsih Hastuti*⁴

1 Akademi Keperawatan YKY Yogyakarta, Indonesia

2 Akademi Keperawatan YKY Yogyakarta, Indonesia

3 Akademi Keperawatan YKY Yogyakarta, Indonesia

4 Fakultas Kedokteran Kesehatan Masyarakat dan keperawatan Universitas Gadjah Mada, Indonesia

5 Residence of Psichiatri Fakultas Kedokteran Kesehatan Masyarakat dan keperawatan Universitas Gadjah Mada, Indonesia

Abstract

Homosexuality has existed along with the development of human civilization and it was perceived differently depending on the local culture. The population of homosexual in the world has been increasing day by day. In 2003-2009, the American Community Survey and the National Health Interview Survey stated that the prevalence of homosexual in United State America was 0,3% from its population. This prevalence become 0,6% in 2016. In Indonesia, there are no definite data about lesbian, gay, bisexual and transgender (LGBT), it is predicted about 3 million people. In 2012, The Ministry of Health estimated that the number of LGBT people in Indonesia is 1,09 million. Homosexual population are often stigmatized and discriminated. This conditions make homosexuals try to change their sexual orientation. The aim of this research was to identify The Effectiveness of The Sexual Orientation Change Effort (Soce) methode for Egodistonic Homosexuality. This research design was literature review. The result showed that this method was not effective.

Keywords: Egodistonic, Homosexual, Soce Methode

Topic: Nursing and anesthesiology

[ABS-41]

Revealing the Experiences of Nursing Students In Psychiatric Hospital Placement: Hidden Challenges in the Covid-19 Era

Ira Kusumawaty, Yunike, Lukman
Politeknik Kesehatan Kemenkes Palembang

Abstract

The coronavirus outbreak has caused multifaceted problems and placed great demands on nursing students at the psychiatric clinical placement. Coping strategies have a significant effect on dealing with stress due to the emotional fluctuation of psychiatric patients which exacerbates the challenges of treating the Covid-19 condition. Exploring the capabilities of these is still very limited, even though understanding about stress and coping strategies are greatly influencing nursing students achievement. This study aims to determine the challenges faced by nursing students while undergoing psychiatric nursing practice during the Covid-19 pandemic. The qualitative research used a phenomenological approach with convenient sampling technique until it reached saturation and recruited nine nursing students. Semi-structured interviews were used to collect data related to participants experiences during clinical placement in mental hospitals. The results of interviews were documented as transcripts and were read repeatedly and data analysis using Colaizzi method to form codes, categorizations and themes. There were two main themes identified, firstly, anxiety when treating patients with Covid-19, including behavior and emotions of psychiatric patients and fear of contracting COVID-19. The second main theme is coping in dealing with stress, which is shown by praying to God, limiting reading social media, protecting oneself and expressing feelings. To evaluate the study, the COREQ checklist was used. The research implication is to accelerate the resolution of clinical practice problems during the Covid-19 period so that optimization of mental nursing clinical practice can be realized through mentoring and managing time for students.

Keywords: Covid-19, hidden challenges, nursing students, psychiatric hospital placement

Topic: Nursing and anesthesiology

[ABS-42]

Parents' experience in giving reproductive health education to children

Dewi Kusumaningtyas (a), Dwi Juwartini (b)
Akademi Keperawatan YKY Yogyakarta

Abstract

Background: children need to know about reproductive health and sexuality from an early age in order to avoid risky sexual behavior and reproductive health problems. Parents have a major role in providing reproductive health education but they have limitation for information. **Purpose of the study:** to find out the description of parents' experience in providing reproductive health education for children. **Research methodology:** Research design was qualitative with a phenomenological approach. This research was carried out from April 2018 to August 2019. This research was conducted at PKK 30 Argomulyo Sedayu Kindergarten, Bantul, Yogyakarta. The population was parents of PKK 30 Kindergarten students Argomulyo Sedayu Bantul. Sampling technique used purposive sampling and adjusted to the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Number of main participants in this study were 8 parents and 1 teacher as supporting participants. The research instrument was the researcher themselves. The data collection used semi-structured interview techniques. Data analysis used Collaizi method. The results of study: was 3 themes, namely- 1) Reproductive health education is provided according to the needs of children, 2) Parents have obstacle in providing reproductive health education, 3) Religion and social norms are considered by parents in providing reproductive health education. Conclusion: It is important that reproductive health education is given to children from an early age and adjusted to the child's developmental stage.

Keywords: Experience, Reproductive Health Education, Children

Topic: Nursing and anesthesiology

[ABS-43]

Psychosocial stress with vaginal discharge of adolescent women in the new normal era in bastiong karance village, ternate*Nurdiana Lante (a*), Istiana Asrari Bansu (b*)*

a) D3 Study Programs, Department of Midwifery, Poltekkes Kemenke Ternate

b) D3 Study Programs, Department of Midwifery, Poltekkes Kemenkes Ternate

Abstract

In the stage of the early development of the adolescent, many led to changes in both the anatomical, physiological, emotional, and intellectual functions and relationships in a social environment. Psychosocial stress experienced by adolescent girls is generally triggered by environmental conditions. Symptoms of stress can be a problem that has an impact on reproductive health such as vaginal discharge. Vaginal discharge is the discharge of fluid not excessive blood from the female genitals (vagina). The purpose of this study is to determine the relationship with the incidence of psychosocial stress whitish young women in the Era of the New Normal. This type of research is correlational. Sampling with non-probability sampling and a sample size of 92 young women. The data collection tool is a questionnaire stress of the Depression Anxiety Stress Scale (DASS 42) and questionnaires incidence of vaginal discharge. Data analysis using Chi-Square test. The results showed that adolescent girls experienced severe stress as many as 52 respondents (56.5%), experienced mild stress 11 respondents (12.0%), adolescents with normal psychosocial stress levels were 29 (31.5%). The adolescents who experienced physiological/normal vaginal discharge were 65 (70.7%) while those who experienced pathological/abnormal vaginal discharge were 27 (29.3%). The results of the statistical test obtained p-value $< (0.016 < 0.05)$. Conclusion: there is a significant relationship between psychosocial stress and female adolescent vaginal discharge complaints in Bastiong Karance Village, with a fairly strong correlation strength. This study recommends the importance of psychological counseling and adolescent reproductive health in the new normal era.

Keywords: Psychosocial Stress, Vaginal Discharge, Adolescent**Topic:** Midwifery

[ABS-44]

Formulation and Sensory Properties of Biscuit with Catfish Substitution as an Additional Foods Alternative for Less Nutritional Children*Yuli Hartati¹, Saprianto², Dika Febriyansari¹, Podojoyo¹, Afriyana Siregar¹, Imelda Telisa¹*

1 Department of Nutrition Poltekkes Kemenkes Palembang, Indonesia

2 Department of Nursing Poltekkes Kemenkes Palembang, Indonesia

Abstract

The incidence of malnutrition in South Sumatra Province in 2018 was 8.40%. The policy of overcoming malnutrition under five by providing additional food (PMT), namely utilizing local food such as catfish flour, purple sweet potato flour, moringa leaf flour, can be processed into biscuits and additional alternative food for malnourished toddlers. This research aims to make a formula for catfish biscuits to determine their acceptability. This research used was experimental using a non-factorial Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with three treatments. The panelists of this research were 25 students of Nutrition from the Poltekkes Kemenkes Palembang. Based on the results of the organoleptic test (taste, texture, aroma, and color), the preferred acceptance of the biscuits catfish was F2 formulation in terms of color, aroma, and taste with a value of 3.14, 3.12, and 3.14. Meanwhile, for the panelist texture, they chose F3 with a value of 2.68. Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that the catfish biscuits are an alternative to additional food for less nutritional children.

Keywords: Biscuits, Formulation, Sensory Properties, Catfish, less nutritional children.**Topic:** Nutrition and Dietetic

[ABS-45]

Kiepoly: Volcano Disaster Mitigation Media for Teenagers Containing Local Wisdom Values of North Maluku Province*Muhamd Faisal Pataha, Arsad Suni*

Poltekkes Kemenkes Ternate

Abstract

Volcanic disaster mitigation, especially in North Maluku Province, is a major factor in the occurrence of natural disasters, this is added to the fact on the ground, especially in volcanically impacted areas, there is no media that can be used as a medium for disaster mitigation in the form of a game in this case monopoly. In addition, there is no media that is characterized by local wisdom, especially the province of North Maluku. The effectiveness of Kiepoly media in increasing knowledge of volcanic disaster mitigation that contains the value of local wisdom in North Maluku province is the goal of this study. The g-test method, which is an analytical technique used to assess and determine the increase in adolescent knowledge about volcanic disaster mitigation is the method used in this study, the measurement of the gain-normalized score is the comparison of the actual gain score with the maximum gain score (Hake, 1999). This study used a pre-experimental Design design, as many as 30 people were used as samples in this study, the inclusion criteria were all teenagers who were registered at SMP Negeri 2 Ternate City and were willing to become respondents, the exclusion criteria were teenagers who were sick or not present at the time of data collection. Targeting is done by using purposive sampling technique. The average pretest and posttest scores increased by 83%, besides the average n-gain score was 0.73 with the High category, which was the result of this study. This proves that Kiepoly media can be used as a medium for disaster mitigation for teenagers which contains the value of local wisdom in North Maluku Province for volcanic disaster mitigation.

Keywords: disaster mitigation- volcano- local culture- kiepoly- north maluku

Topic: Nursing and anesthesiology

[ABS-46]

The Effect of Story Play Therapy in Language Development Children with Mental Retardation at SLB Rela Bhakti I, Gamping, Sleman, Yogyakarta, Indonesia*Rahmita Nuril Amalia1*, Tri Arini2*

1 Academy of Nursing YKY Yogyakarta, Indonesia

2 Academy of Nursing YKY Yogyakarta, Indonesia

Abstract

Background: Retardation mental is child who has lack ability of adaptive behavior and intellectuals below average that appears during development process. The emergence of various developmental barriers in children with mental retardation is a phenomenon that needs to be further addressed so that the children with mental retardation can still live a good life and optimize the slightest their abilities, including increasing language skills. Purpose: To determine the effect of story play therapy on language development in children with mental retardation at SLB Rela Bhakti I Gamping Sleman Yogyakarta. Method: The type of research is Quasi-experimental with the design of ^Pre-test Post-test with Control Group Design^. The result of examination data was analysed descriptively and analytically by using SPSS for windows version 16.0 with Paired Samples Test, for a significant level of 0.05. Results: The results of the Paired Samples Test in the treatment group showed that the p value was = <0.001 ($p < 0.05$) and the CI 95% was between -5.91 to -2.76 and it did not pass 0 (zero), statistically it shows that there was a significant difference in the mean language development of children before and after giving story play therapy. Whereas the control group showed that the p value = 0.49 (> 0.05) and 95% CI between -0.28 to 0.55 and exceeding 0 (zero). Therefore, there was no difference in the mean language development of children for before and after giving story play therapy. Conclusion: Story play therapy can improve language development in children with mental retardation at SLB Rela Bhakti I Gamping Sleman Yogyakarta.

Keywords: story play therapy, language development, mental retardation children

Topic: Nursing and anesthesiology

[ABS-47]

The Effect of Accupressure Technique on Breast Milk Production Postpartum Mother at Rajawali Citra Hospital, Yogyakarta, Indonesia*Rahmita Nuril Amalia^{1*}, Tri Arini², Viantika Kusumasari³*

1 Academy of Nursing YKY Yogyakarta, Indonesia

2 Academy of Nursing YKY Yogyakarta, Indonesia

3 Surya Global Institute Health Science

Abstract

Background: One of the problems experienced by postpartum mothers is one that is not smooth milk production, this is an obstacle for mothers to give breast milk to babies. As for ways to facilitate the production of breast milk, namely by using acupressure techniques, this technique can help increase the hormone prolactin and oxytocin to influence milk production. Objective: To determine the effect of acupressure on breast milk production in postpartum mothers at RSU Rajawali Citra Yogyakarta. Method: This study uses a quasy design experimental pre-test and post-test nonequivalent with control group. The sampling technique used was consecutive sampling. The number of samples was 20 postpartum mothers in RSU Rajawali Citra Yogyakarta (10 intervention groups and 10 control groups). The research instrument used to measure breast milk production was a 250 ml measuring cup. Data analysis used with paired t-test and independent t-test. Results: The results of the independent t-test showed a significance value ($p = 0.001$), a p value of <0.05 , which meant that there was a significant difference in effect between acupressure and oxytocin massage on breast milk production in the intervention and control groups. Conclusion: There is an effect of the acupressure technique on breast milk production in postpartum mothers at RSU Rajawali Citra Yogyakarta.

Keywords: acupressure, breast milk production, postpartum**Topic:** Midwifery

[ABS-48]

Relationship Consumption of Macro Nutrients, Body mass index, Smoking status with Physical Fitness at Palembang Police District*Podojoyo, Tria Erma Juliana, Susyani, Yuli Hartati, Muhamad Taswin, Zainal Abidin*
Poltekkes Palembang**Abstract**

Physical fitness is the ability and ability of the body to make adjustments to the physical burden given to members of the police in carrying out daily work without causing excessive fatigue and still be able to enjoy their free time. Components of physical freshness related to health and skills are cardiorespiratory, muscle endurance, muscle strength and body composition. The purpose of this study was to determine the relationship between macronutrient consumption, body mass index status, and smoking status with physical fitness values at Palembang police district officers. Intake of macro nutrients taken using the recall method one times 24 hours. Physical fitness levels are measured using Cooper's way. The design of this study was Cross-sectional by taking a random sample of 56 male police officers.

The analysis results using chi-square concluded there is a relationship between energy intake, carbohydrate intake, with fitness level ($p \leq 0.05$). There is a relationship between body mass index and smoking status, and physical fitness ($p \leq 0.05$). There is no relationship between protein and fat intake with physical fitness status ($p > 0.05$). The results of the multivariate analysis obtained the most dominant relationship with physical fitness levels is BMI status and smoking status. It is recommended that police members improve physical fitness status to take some exercises that are useful to enhance physical fitness levels, namely sit ups, push-ups, squat jumps to run or jogging regularly. Police officers control their ideal weight by eating a balanced diet and not smoking.

Keywords: physical fitness, body mass index, energy intake, smoking

Topic: Nutrition and Dietetic

[ABS-49]

Analysis Online Learning Readiness in Preparing for Nursing Anesthesia Fieldwork Competency Practices*Kania Ratna Arimbi(1*), Bondan Palestin (2)*

(1)Department of Nursing Poltekkes Kemenkes Yogyakarta, Indonesia.

(2) Department of Nursing Poltekkes Kemenkes Yogyakarta, Indonesia.

Abstract

In attempt to suppress the growth of the Corona Virus cases Indonesian government issued several policies, one of them is implementing online learning from home method. Vocational students are one of those affected levels by the use of this method whose more skill-oriented than theoretical oriented. This study aims to perceive the level readiness against online learning at the practice course at vocational education during the Corona Virus pandemic. Elements assessed on this study are technological preparedness, self-motivational learner and practical skills. This research is an observational cross-sectional study. The population in this study was the Applied Bachelor of Nursing Anesthesia in Health Polytechnic of Ministry of Health Yogyakarta and Siti Aisyah University Yogyakarta. The samples taken by using purposive random sampling method on students who are undergoing online learning in this pandemic and have done or currently running a hospital clinical practice. The data collected using Online Readiness Assessment by Vicki Williams combined with clinical practice skills criteria for applied bachelor of nursing anesthesia students. The data analysis technique is qualitative analysis consisting of data collection, data reduction, data presentation and conclusion. The result showed students readiness in each aspects are 44% in technology self-efficacy, 56% in self-directed learning, 55% in learner control, 61% in motivation for learning, 60% in online communication self-efficacy, and 51% in anesthesia fieldwork competencies practice.

Keywords: Online Learning- Student Perception- Anesthesia Fieldwork Practices**Topic:** Nursing and anesthesiology

[ABS-50]

Health Promotion Strategy Through Family Approach And Community Empowerment For Reducing The Risk Of Non-Communicable Disease In Denpasar*Ni Komang Wiardani, I Wayan Juni Arsana, Mahesa Dwipayani*

Nutrition Departement, Poltekkes Kemenkes Denpasar

Abstract

Non Communicable Diseases (NCD) is a global health problem that's increase every year. NCD must be addressed immediately considering this disease, especially cardiovascular and diabetes mellitus are the main cause of death in world population. The study aims to determine the effectiveness of health promotion strategies through family approach and community empowerment for reducing the risk of NCD in Denpasar. The study was an intervention with a pre-post-test control group design. Subjects were family members who were at risk of NCD (obesity, hyperglycemia or hypertension), divided into two groups were control and treatment groups consist of 42 people of each group. Data were collected include identity, diet, physical activity, blood glucose and blood pressure. The intervention were conducted among 3 months. The results of study that the study was conducted by subjects with a risk of non-communicable diseases, amount of 42 people to each group, with male of 42.95% in the treatment group and 57.1% of female. The average energy intake of subjects was 1675.4 kcal/day and 56.3% for control group and 59.4% of the control group had an intake above of adequacy rate. A total of 33.3% of the treatment group and 38, 1% of the control group had smoking history, 43.3% low level physical activity. The BMI indicator, waist circumference, blood pressure and blood glucose showed significant differences after intervention ($p < 0.05$) and intervention was effective to reduce the risk of NCD indicators. There was decreased indicators by intervention, such as BMI 1.9 kg / m², waist circumference 2.2 cm, blood pressure 21.1/5.2 mmHg and blood glucose decreased by 24.2 mg/dl. The results of this study show that's an intervention has a dominant effect on changes of NCD indicators.

Keywords: NCD, health promotion, family approach, community empowerment**Topic:** Public Health

[ABS-51]

Hypnobreastfeeding Android Application for Woman Breastfeeding Anxiety*Kharisma Virgian(a)*, Desy Setiawati(a), Ratnaningsih Dewi Astuti(a)*

Poltekkes Kemenkes Palembang

Jalan Jend.Sudirman KM.3,5 Komp. RSMH Palembang,Indonesia 30126

*kharismavirgian@gmail.com

Abstract

In the process of breastfeeding, there will be many problems faced. One of the problems that arise is anxiety. A breastfeeding mother worries about whether she will breastfeed her baby well and often feels insecure. The way to overcome the stress of breastfeeding mothers is to give Hypnobreastfeeding. The Hypnobreastfeeding technique given is giving positive affirmations through audio and visuals from android-based applications. This study aims to influence the Hypnobreastfeeding.Android Application on breastfeeding women in The Midwife Independent Practice of Palembang. His research uses non-random sampling with a sample size of 67 respondents. Quasi Experiment research design using a pretest and posttest control-group design approach. Measuring breastfeeding women's anxiety levels before and after being given. Hypnobreastfeeding Android Application using the HARS (Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale) instrument. The results showed a significant difference between breastfeeding women's anxiety levels before and after being given Hypnobreastfeeding Android Application with Wilcoxon Test $p = 0,000 (< \alpha = 0,005)$. The suggestion in this study was that breastfeeding mothers must have high self-confidence and always feel happy to undergo the breastfeeding process well.

Keywords: Hypnobreastfeeding android application- breastfeeding anxiety**Topic:** Midwifery

[ABS-52]

Potency of Some Foods as Antiviral in Protecting from Covid-19

Badrut Tamam (a)- I Gst Putu Sudita Puryana (b)- I G.A. Ari Widarti (b)- Suratiah (c)*

a*) Nutrition Department, Polytechnic of Health Denpasar, Bali
badruttamam_70@yahoo.com

b) Nutrition Department, Polytechnic of Health Denpasar, Bali

c) Nursing Department, Polytechnic of Health Denpasar, Bali

Abstract

The outbreak of the corona virus disease (Covid-19) causing severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS-CoV-2) has become a global pandemic. The role of food in the treatment of Covid-19 is still an interesting topic of debate. However, several studies have reported the presence of antiviral compounds in several foods, such as tea, fermented vegetables and fermented milk. Therefore, it is important to investigate the potential for foods that have anti-viral properties to increase the immune system, and in turn to reduce the sickness and death rates due to Covid-19. This study was designed using a systematic review, by collecting secondary data and publication of qualified international and national scientific journals that were analyzed by meta-analysis. Data sources and publications from these journals are used to compile the types of food, the active compounds they have and the mechanism of action of these foods as antivirals. There are several types of foods that have antiviral activity, including honey, moringa, fermented food, tea and guava. The mechanism of actions of the foods in preventing and overcoming viral infections are different among the foods, such as antiviral activities and preventing hiperinflammation by SARS-CoV-2 (honey)- immunebooster, antiviral, inhibiting virus replication cycle (moringa)- immunebooster, reducing virus permeability, antiinflammation, and viral trap (fermented foods)- trapping virus hemagglutinin (tea)- competitive inhibition during virus replication (guava). The dominant bioactive compounds present in the foods against virus activities are fenol, flavonoids, vitamin C, resin, alkaloids, tanin, saponin, antraquinon, kaempferol, pterygosperm, morphine, quercetine, glycoside, Theaflavin, Lactobacillus and Bifidobacterium.

Keywords: Antiviral- Covid-19- Flavonoids- Foods

Topic: Nutrition and Dietetic

[ABS-53]

Snakes and Ladders Game Innovation as Local Wisdom to Increase Knowledge and Change in Dental and Oral Health Behavior in Al Barokah Semarang Orphanage Children

1.Sukinia 2.Jeineke E Ratuela 3.Fuad Faturrohman 4.Dwi Suyatmid 5. Indah Febriyanti

1. Politeknik Kesehatan Kemenkes Semarang
2. Poltekkes Kemenkes Manado
3. Fakultas Kedokteran Gigi Universitas Muhammadiyah Semarang
4. Poltekkes Kemenkes Yogyakarta
5. Poltekkes Kemenkes Semarang

Abstract

The traditional game of snakes and ladders is a local wisdom, educative for children to play while learning so that it can be used to increase knowledge and skills of dental health. The purpose of this study was to design an innovative snake and ladder game that serves to increase knowledge about dental and oral health. This research is the development of existing research. In this study, an innovation of the snake and ladder game was developed for dental and oral health. Research design *quasi experiment* by design *Pretest-Posttest control group design*. The sample is elementary school age children at the Al Barokah Orphanage. 17 children became the control group and 17 as the neutral group. The independent variable is Snake Ladder Game Innovation, the dependent variable is knowledge and changes in dental health behavior, with instruments in the form of a questionnaire and a check list of 25 questions on an ordinal scale of pre-test and post-test instruments.. The most pre-test results with sufficient knowledge category are 22 respondents (64.7 %), the most final knowledge score (Posttest) with good knowledge category is 26 respondents (76.4%). The results of the Mann Whitney statistical test showed that there was a difference between the experimental group and the control group on dental and oral health knowledge with a value of $0.02 < 0.05$. The results of the *Wilcoxon Test* statistical test showed that there was a difference between the *Pretest* and *Posttest* of the experimental group with a value of $0.00 < 0.05$ and the control group with a value of $0.00 < 0.05$. The results of the *Mann Whitney* statistical test showed that there was a difference between the experimental group and the control group on dental and oral health knowledge with a value of $0.02 < 0.05$.

Keywords: snake ladder, knowledge, behavior, dental health

Topic: Oral and Dental Health

[ABS-55]

Ethyl Acetate And Ethanol Extract Of Leaf *Abrus precatorius* L. As Inhibitors Against Biofilm Formation *Staphylococcus aureus* Strains Methicillin Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) 22372 Indonesia Local Isolate*Bq. Mutmainnah (a)*, Ni[^]matuzahroh (b), Afaf Baktir (c)*a) Akademi Kesehatan Gigi Karya Adi Husada Mataram,
Indonesia*Bmmasadepan9@gmail.com

b), c) Faculty of Sains and Technology, Universitas Airlangga, Indonesia

Abstract

Isolate of *Staphylococcus* bacteria with code MRSA 22372 Indonesian Local Isolate (ILI) was derived from the urine of patients at RSUD Dr. Soetomo, Clinical Microbiology Installation Surabaya, Indonesia. The level of polarity of the solvent affects the inhibition of bacterial cell growth. The active ingredient of *Abrus precatorius* L. leaf extract has the potential to inhibit the growth of bacterial biofilms. This study aimed to compare the growth inhibitory activity of the bacterial biofilm MRSA 22372 ILI due to various treatments of ethyl acetate and ethanol extract of *A. precatorius* L. leaves from concentrations of 25 mgL⁻¹ to 800 mgL⁻¹. The results showed that the total flavonoid content of the ethyl acetate and ethanol extract of the leaves of *A. precatorius* L. were obtained respectively 241.67 mg CE/g and 205 mg CE/g. Ethyl acetate and ethanol extract of *A. precatorius* L. leaves inhibited MRSA 22372 ILI biofilm by 62.9% and 71.4%, respectively. Ethanol extract of *A. precatorius* L. leaf inhibited the growth of MRSA 22372 ILI biofilm higher than that of *A. precatorius* L. ethyl acetate leaf extract. Minimum Biofilm Inhibition Concentration (MBIC) value of MRSA 22372 ILI by ethyl acetate and ethanol extract of *A. precatorius* L. leaf 25 mg/L by 14.3%. Administration of ethyl acetate and ethanol extract of *A. precatorius* L. leaves at higher concentrations was required to achieve the eradication effect of MRSA 22372 ILI biofilm. The inhibitory effect of MRSA 22372 ILI biofilm growth by ethyl acetate and ethanol extract of *A. precatorius* L. leaves showed good inhibition *in vitro*, and further research is needed in clinical conditions *in vivo*.

Keywords: Ethyl acetate and ethanol extract, *Abrus precatorius* L., Inhibitor, biofilm, *S. aureus*, MRSA 22372 ILI

Topic: Medical Laboratory Technology

[ABS-56]

Implementation of Transtheoretical Model of Nutrition Education and Chromium Picolinate Supplementation on Dietary Adherence Behavior, Chromium Consumption Pattern and Blood Glucose Level Diabetes Mellitus Patients*Lely Cintari dan DP Sukraniti*

Nutrition Department, Health Polytechnic in Denpasar, Indonesia

Abstract

Bali is one of the provinces in Indonesia that has a Diabetes Mellitus rate above the national prevalence. According to the results of the 2020 study, 56.9% of DM patients did not understand diet education and did not comply with the diet by 56.9% with abnormal blood glucose levels of 63.9%. The results confirmed that repeated exposure with the right method, especially with The theoretical model is very effective in increasing knowledge and adherence to diet and chromium consumption patterns in DM patients. Chromium has been shown to be effective in improving blood glucose levels in people with Diabetes Mellitus (Types 1 and 2). Chromium improves glucose metabolism in patients with prediabetic glucose intolerance and in all women with gestational diabetes. The purpose of this study was to determine the role of nutrition education using a transtheoretical model and the effect of chromium picolinate supplementation on dietary adherence behavior, chromium consumption patterns and blood glucose levels in patients with diabetes mellitus. This type of research is quasi-experimental. The research design used was one group pretest-posttest. This design does not use a comparison group (control), but uses the first observation (pretest) which allows testing the changes that occur after the experiment or program (Notoatmodjo, 2010). The study was conducted at the Denpasar Health Center. The results showed that there were differences in the level of knowledge and consumption of chromium and blood glucose levels in DM patients. However, there was no difference in the attitude and level of dietary compliance of DM patients.

Keywords: TM Nutrition Education, Chromium Picolinate, Dietary Adherence Behavior, Blood Glucose Level, Diabetes Mellitus

Topic: Nutrition and Dietetic

[ABS-57]

Potential effect of ethyl acetate extract Of *Mimosa pudica* L. against Biofilm Formation of *Streptococcus mutans**Supnawadi(a), Bq. Mutmainnah(b)**

Akademi Kesehatan Gigi Karya Adi Husada Mataram

Abstract

The formation of *S. mutans* biofilms can survive in extreme environments and is more resistant to antibiotics. The ethyl acetate extract of *M. pudica* L. contains tannins and flavonoids which are known to inhibit the expression of the intercellular adhesion (*ica*) gene which is a regulator of *S. mutans* biofilm formation. The aim of the study was to compare the anti-biofilm ability of *M. pudica* at various concentrations of *S. mutans* biofilm. The methods used in this study include extraction of *M. pudica* L. by maceration method using ethyl acetate solvent, morphological and physiological analysis of *S. mutans* using the Microbact TM. Potential inhibition of biofilm growth of *S. mutans* cells by Microtiter Plate Biofilm Assay method using ELISA reader and Total Plate Count. Surface morphological analysis of *S. mutans* biofilm was carried out by Scanning Electron Microscopy. The results showed that *S. mutans* formed the enzymes nitrate, glucose, mannitol, ONPG, urease, sucrose and catalase. Ethyl acetate extract of *M. pudica* L. could significantly inhibit biofilm formation with an effect of 78.7% with a Minimum Biofilm Inhibitory Concentration (MBIC) of 50 mg mL⁻¹. The number of living bacterial cells in the biofilm of *S. mutans* cells was 81.2%. The benefits of the research are expected to be the ability of *M. pudica* L. extract as an antibiofilm against *S. mutans* and can be used as an alternative treatment for *S. mutans* infection.

Keywords: ethyl acetate extract, *M. pudica* L., biofilm formation, *Streptococcus mutans*

Topic: Medical Laboratory Technology

[ABS-58]

Modification of Traditional Balinese Food as disaster emergency food*Ni Putu Agustini, I G.P.Sudita Puryana, I Komang Agusjaya Mataram*

Poltekkes Kemenkes Denpasar

Abstract

This study aimed to make disaster formula food based on traditional Balinese local food quality, nutritious, safe and in accordance with Balinese culture so that it can be accepted to cope with food availability in a state of disaster. The development of the disaster formula is based on the traditional Balinese jaja satu meal made from glutinous rice flour and brown sugar with the substitution of treatment using green beans powder, peanuts, and cashews as a source of protein, and Moringa leaf powder as a source of food fiber. The study was designed in a randomized block design with six formulations and three replications. The results showed that the selected treatment of the formulation was F4 (20 g glutinous rice flour, 25g peanut powder, 5 g Moringa leaf powder, and 50 g brown sugar) with a degree of preference for color, flavour, texture, taste and overall acceptance of the like value. This modification formula has a water content of 7.18%, ash 1.34%, protein 16.41%, fat 13.53%, carbohydrates 61.48%, food fiber 18.87%, Fe 6.23 ppm and total energy of 433.27 per 100 gram formula. This formula is microbiologically safe with a shelf life of 10 days. One portion of Balinese traditional local food-based disaster formula as much as 50 g can contribute energy of 216.64 kcal (10.31%), protein 8,205 g (16.41%), and fat 6.765 g (16.91%) for the standard emergency food is 2100 kcal, 50 g protein and 40 g fat.

Keywords: disaster food, local Balinese food, nutrition quality, sensory quality

Topic: Nutrition and Dietetic

[ABS-59]

The difference of maternal brain derived neurotrophic factor and Total Score Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale between low and normal ferritin among pregnant women

Ayi Diah Damayani (a), Eka Safitri Yanti (b)*

- a) Pusat Unggulan Institusi, Poltekkes Kemenkes Pangkalpinang, Bangka Belitung, Indonesia
*damayani.ayidiah@gmail.com
- b) Pusat Unggulan Institusi, Poltekkes Kemenkes Pangkalpinang, Bangka Belitung, Indonesia

Abstract

Background and Objective Maternal iron deficiency anemia is thought to be related to postpartum depressive in biology pathway Ferritin is the first test to become abnormal as iron stores decrease and it is not affected by recent iron ingestion Furthermore, iron deficiency anemia also can decrease Brain Derived Neurotrophic Factor BDNF which play role in sinaps plasticity in neuron The purpose of this study is to determinate difference of maternal BDNF and total score Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale EPDS between low and normal ferritin among pregnant women Methods and Study Design This was an observational study with a cross sectional design at Health Center Care Lubuk Buaya Padang and Biomedical Laboratory Faculty of Medicine Andalas University in Indonesia in November 2016 to June 2017 Samples in this study are 72 pregnant women in 37 until 42 weeks pregnancy were divided to 2 groups which are low 12 ng/mL and normal ferritin 12 ngmL Ferritin and BDNF measured with ELISA after examination and EPDS were assessed at 2 weeks after delivery Data analysed using independent t test Result The average serum BDNF in low ferritin pregnant women was 3.32 3.95 ngmL and normal ferritin was 3.71 4.87 ngmL p 0,299. The average total score EPDS in low ferritin was 11,31 2,175 and normal ferritin was 6,69 3,104 p 0,000 Conclusion There was significant difference in total score EPDS but not serum BDNF between low and normal ferritin among pregnant women.

Keywords: Ferritin, Brain Derived Neurotrophic Factor, Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale, Anemia, Iron Deficiency Anemia

Topic: Midwifery

[ABS-60]

Patterns in dealing with cardiac arrest in the environment family in North Maluku Province*Wasis Nugroho, S.Kep, Ns, M.Kep (a) 2.Aminudin Muhammad, S.Kep, M.Kes (b)*

Poltekkes Kemenkes Ternate (a)&(b)

Abstract

Cardiac arrest is an emergency problem of heart disease that is so deadly that it requires quick and precise treatment. The family as the first person (Bystander) to find individuals with cardiac arrest events has a very important position in saving the lives of sufferers. The purpose of this study is to find out the design of a generalization of bystanders when dealing with people who experience cardiac arrest in the family environment in North Maluku Province. Qualitative research method using Grounded Theory approach that can later develop a concept in the form of design of a constructive analytical scheme that is still regional scale. Data coding using CAQDAS Atlas-ti version 2019. The results of this study found nine themes related to five family patterns in dealing with cardiac arrest events in the family environment, among others- knowing the symptoms before the event, not knowing the symptoms before the incident, finding signs during the incident, understanding when facing problems, initial decisions, taking action, seeking health care, wanting hope and feelings that arise. Health Agencies need to map this known rescue link as a planning in providing socialization and training as an effort to prevent the occurrence of cardiac arrests in the area.

Keywords: cardiac arrest, family, bystander**Topic:** Nursing and anesthesiology

[ABS-61]

**Factors-associated with life satisfaction among people with edentulism in Indonesia:
A data analysis from IFLS-5***Septika Priskasari (a*), Elastria Widita (b)*

(a*) Dental Hygiene Research Division, Indonesian Dental Hygienist Association, Yogyakarta

(b)Dental Hygiene Program, Faculty of Dentistry, Universitas Gadjah Mada, Yogyakarta

Abstract

As an indicator of the quality of life, life satisfaction can be affected by many aspects, including oral health conditions. Edentulism is a condition when people lose all their permanent teeth and frequently occurs in the elderly. Among those who had edentulism, people may experience different levels of life satisfaction depending on their background, behavior, and environment. This research aimed to explore the factors associated with life satisfaction among people with edentulism. This cross-sectional study utilized and analyzed secondary data from the Indonesian Family Life Survey (IFLS-5) conducted nationally in 2014-2015. Life satisfaction as a dependent variable was obtained from IFLS-5 questionnaires, as well as other explanatory variables. Chi-square test, Fisher's exact test, and logistic regression analysis were used to determine the association between and among variables. The prevalence of edentulism in the Indonesian population was 5.8%. The bivariate analysis found that people's concerns for food consumption, healthcare, health perception, and religiosity were associated with life satisfaction ($p < 0.05$). Then, these factors were run further into logistic regression. Among 396 people with edentulism, those who have good health perceptions were likely to have higher life satisfaction ($OR = 1.82$, $p < 0.05$). Although other variables were found to be insignificantly contributed, the odds ratio showed that those who had adequate concern for food consumption ($OR = 1.72$) and healthcare ($OR = 1.77$) were likely to experience higher life satisfaction. Moreover, those who considered themselves religious ($OR = 4.91$) were likely to have four times higher life satisfaction than those who did not. In conclusion, this analysis suggests that health perception was the strongest contributed factor to life satisfaction among people with edentulism in Indonesia. Further observation involving more explanatory variables and longitudinal data is recommended.

Keywords: life satisfaction, edentulism, health perception, religiosity, IFLS**Topic:** Oral and Dental Health

[ABS-62]

The utilization of medicinal plants as a traditional drug in public women in The Region Kecamatan Mentok Kabupaten Bangka Barat In 2020*Eva Dewi R Purba (a)- Rachmawati Felani Djuria (a dan b*)- M.Seto Sudirman (a)*

- a. Pharmacy Departement, Polytechnic of Health, Ministry of Health, Pangkalpinang
 - b. Science and Technology Center of Excellence, Polytechnic of Health, Ministry of Health, Pangkalpinang
- * felandj87@gmail.com

Abstract

Many types of plants can be explored as ingredients in traditional medicine. One of the uses of plants as traditional medicine is herbal concoctions for postpartum mothers. Traditional healers (Hatra) use herbal ingredients in the treatment of post-partum mothers who have prepared these herbs in ready-to-use medicinal dosage forms (solid dosage forms such as pills, powders and parem). The use of herbs or herbs should pay attention to the aspects of monitoring the distribution and supervision of traditional medicines. This community service activity is carried out with the aim of increasing public knowledge in the form of training in making traditional medicines and providing information related to registration and distribution permits for traditional medicines. The method used in this service is providing counseling, discussion and training in making traditional medicines in the treatment of postpartum mothers. The results of this service activity resulted in 4 traditional herbal remedies for delivery, namely parem stomach and body parem to clean dirt / dirty blood, brewed herbal medicine to remove stiffness / increase stamina and brewed herbal medicine to avoid colds. The conclusion is that service activities are effective in increasing skills in making traditional herbal medicine for delivery and increasing the number of people who know how to make herbal medicine for delivery, which so far has only decreased in one family.

Keywords: Traditional Medicine, Postpartum, Mentok

Topic: Community Empowerment

[ABS-63]

Comparison of neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) among negative and confirmed positive for Covid-19 patients at RSUD Wates*Siti Zainatun Wasilah¹, Arma Wulan Mardhika², Bambang Supriyanta³*POLTEKKES KEMENKES YOGYAKARTA
JURUSAN ANALIS KESEHATAN**Abstract**

A pneumonia case with an unknown etiology was first discovered in Wuhan, Hubei Province in Desember 2019. WHO (World health Organization) announced that the new coronavirus disease discovered in Hubei Province, China was a Public Health Emergency of International Concern (PHIEC). Covid-19 is novel disease that has never been previously identified in humans. The etiology of this illness was attributed to a novel virus called SARS-COV-2. WHO stated that there was a high risk of Coronavirus 2019 (Covid-19) spreading to other surrounding countries so it decided to call Covid-19 a pandemic. The Covid-19 case in Indonesia was first discovered on 2nd March 2020. The recommended method for detecting the SARS-COV-2 virus is nucleic acid amplification with real-time Reverse Transcription Polymerase Chain Reaction (rRT-PCR). Several blood components that are widely used as a monitoring tool and predictor of Covid-19 are the level of leukocytes, lymphocytes, neutrophils, platelets, and the neutrophil-lymphocyte ratio. This study aims to determine the difference in the levels of the Neutrophil-to- Lymphocyte Ratio (NLR) among negative and confirmed positive for Covid-19 patients who were hospitalized at Wates Regional General Hospital. This was an observational analytical study with cross sectional approach. The samples were negative and confirmed positive Covid-19 patients who were hospitalized at Wates Regional General Hospital in March-August 2020 who had been tested for Netrophil-to-Lymphocyte Ratio (NLR). The data obtained were using a statistical test for two independent samples of Mann-Whitney U test which obtain a significant value (p) of 0.000 or $p < 0.05$. Thus, it can be concluded that there was a difference in the levels of Netrophil-to-Lymphocyte Ration (NLR) between negative and confirmed positive for Covid-19 patients who were hospitalized at Wates Regional General Hospital.

Keywords: Netrophil-to-Lymphocyte Ratio (NLR), rRT-PCR, Covid-19**Topic:** Medical Laboratory Technology

[ABS-64]

Social capital and social impact in waste management of the waste bank system in Yogyakarta Indonesia*Sri Haryanti¹, Evi Gravitariani², Mahendra Wijaya³, Adhy Timur Hartanto⁴*

1 Lecturer of Environmental Health Poltekkes Kemenkes Yogyakarta

2 Lecturer of Post Graduate Program, Sebelas Maret University (UNS)

3 Lecturer of Social and Political Science Faculty, Sebelas Maret University (UNS)

4 Sanitarian of Puskesmas Wirobrajan, Yogyakarta

Abstract

Waste bank is one of trash management using 3R (Reuse, Reduce, Recycle) in waste management at its source at community level. The scheme of waste bank is based on the application of social capital covering the core elements of the implementation of social capital that are trust, norm, network, reciprocity and value. This research aims to examine the relationship between social capital and social impact of waste management using waste bank Programme in Yogyakarta, Indonesia. This paper studied social impacts which cover income raising, employment and environmental hygiene. The study was conducted in October-December 2016. The subjects in this study were 100 customers of waste bank of 5 locations in Yogyakarta. This study employ spearman correlation to analyze the data using SPSS 16. The results reveal the correlation between social capital and social impact to increasing income and employment is weak. It is showed by the values of coefficient of correlation (r) are 0,111 and 0,095 respectively with significant value of $0.346 > 0.05$. Furthermore, the correlation between social capital and social impact to environmental hygiene has a fairly is strong with coefficient value (r) of 0.454 at significant level of $0.00 < 0.05$.

Keywords: waste bank, social capital, social impact**Topic:** Environmental Health

[ABS-65]

**The effect of fat intake and fiber intake on the adults central obesity in the
Girimaya Health Center, Pangkalpinang***Ade Devriany (a*), Endah Mayang Sari (a), Ori Pertami Enardi (a), Emmy Kardinasari (a)*

a) Nutrition, Health Polytechnic of the Ministry of Health Pangkalpinang, Pangkalpinang City,
Bangka Belitung

Abstract

According to the Riskesdas result in 2013 there are 18 provinces that have central obesity prevalence above the national average and one of them is Bangka Belitung province. Central obesity can occur because of changes in lifestyle such as high consumption of alcoholic beverages, smoking, high consumption of fatty foods, low consumption of vegetables and fruit, as well as lack of physical activity. The majority of Indonesia's population consume 15 grams of fiber/person/day, whereas the consumption of good fiber ranges from 25 grams/day. Nationally, the average fat intake in Indonesia amounted to 41.9 grams. In Bangka Belitung Islands alone the average fat intake in adults was 58.2 grams (Balitbangkes, 2014). This research is analytical survey with cross sectional study. The subjects in this study were all adults aged 18-55 years that recorded in the inspection report of Girimaya PHC and 158 people was selected as sample thus meet the inclusion criteria for the study by using accidental sampling technique. In this study data was collected using secondary data and primary data (anthropometry size, fat and fiber intake). Data analysis is done gradually by univariate, bivariate (Kendall tau correlation test) and multivariate (logistic regression analysis). The results of this study suggest that fat intake has a positive effect on the incidence of central obesity on adults in Girimaya PHC Pangkalpinang district with correlation coefficient of 0.744. While fiber intake had a negative effect on the incidence of central obesity on adults in Girimaya PHC Pangkalpinang district with correlation coefficient of -0.370.

Keywords: Central Obesity, Fat Intake, Fiber Intake

Topic: Nutrition and Dietetic

[ABS-66]

Medical record borrowing control tools design: tracer and outguide*Aqsalsa Setya Sabila1**, *Anton Kristijono2*, *Niko Tesni Saputro3*

1 Department of Medical Record and Health Information Poltekkes Kemenkes Semarang, Indonesia

2 Department of Medical Record and Health Information Poltekkes Kemenkes Semarang, Indonesia

3 Department of Midwifery Poltekkes Kemenkes Yogyakarta, Indonesia

Abstract

A tracer is an important tool in controlling the borrowing of medical records. It is put in the bag contained in the outguide, which is a substitute for guidelines for exiting the medical record file. A preliminary study at General Regional Hospital RAA Soewondo Pati found that the tracer was not used, and the outguide had not been used according to its designation. The use of both tools is regulated through the SOP of medical record borrowing. The misfile cases are still high. This study is a qualitative research, aiming to design a tracer and redesign the outguide as a control tool of medical records in the medical record unit to reduce the misfile cases. Data were obtained through observation (non-participant) and interviews. The results of the tracer design and the outguide redesign were tested to see the level of acceptance of officers. Data analysis used the Miles and Huberman model by following some steps including data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing. The results of this study show that the filing clerk did not apply the procedures as set in the SOP. The tracer design includes information about the name of the hospital, the patient's medical record number, the date and time the tracer was discharged, the patient's name, the patient's address, the poly or the intended service and the name of the doctor in charge of services. The outguide redesign is rectangular in landscape orientation with 35.4 cm length, 12 cm width, 0.7 mm thickness- this makes the outguide stand out compared to the length of the map. The outguide redesign uses polypropylene plastic. There is a tracer pocket on the left side of the outguide. Improvements to the SOP for borrowing outpatient medical record files are emphasized on the use of tracers and outguide as guidelines for outpatient medical record files being borrowed. The three respondents gave positive feedback to the tracer design and outguide redesign.

Keywords: medical record borrowing- design- tracer- outguide

Topic: Medical Record and Health Information

[ABS-67]

The relationship of knowledge and attitude of housewives with the utilization of The Kebumen Gemilang Sejahtera Waste Bank In Ilir Timur Ii District of Palembang*Khairil Anwar¹, Diah Navianti², Muhamad Taswin,³ Amik,⁴*

Politechnic of Health in Palembang

Abstract

Waste banks can play a role in solving the waste problem as a whole, and the waste management system with savings through a waste bank also involves the participation of the community to jointly manage waste. The purpose of this study was to determine the relationship between the knowledge and attitudes of housewives with the utilization of the Kebumen Gemilang Sejahtera waste bank in Ilir Timur Dua District of Palembang. This research is an observational study with a cross sectional approach. The research subjects were housewives in Ilir Timur Dua District as many as 100 people. The Data was collected by interview method using a questionnaire (knowledge, attitude, and utilization). The results of the study using the Chi Square Test method showed that there was a significant relationship between the knowledge of housewives and the use of waste banks ($P \text{ value } 0.005 < \alpha = 0.05$ OR = 14.7) and there was a significant relationship between the attitudes of housewives and the use of waste banks. waste bank ($P \text{ value } 0.003 < = 0.05$ OR=16,4). The conclusion in the study is the knowledge and attitudes of housewives have a relationship with the utilization of the Kebumen Gemilang Sejahtera waste bank in Ilir Timur Dua District of Palembang. Housewives who have good knowledge have 14.7 times the opportunity to use the Kebumen Gemilang Sejahtera waste bank. Housewives who have a good attitude have 16.4 times the opportunity to take advantage of the Kebumen Gemilang Sejahtera waste bank. Recommended to housewives to increase the utilization of the waste bank and to sort the waste first before the waste is saved to the waste bank and to the manager of the Kebumen Gemilang Sejahtera Waste Bank to increase the socialization of the use of the Waste Bank to the public.

Keywords: Knowledge, Attitude, Utilization of Waste Banks.**Topic:** Environmental Health

[ABS-68]

A comparative of antioxidant activity and total phenol between tea from a lowland plantation in Bangka Belitung Island and tea from commercial brands*Novidiyanto (a*), Sutyanawan (b)*

Departement of Nutrition, Poltekkes Kemenkes Pangkalpinang
*novidi2011@gmail.com

Abstract

Several studies explain that tea is a functional drink contains active components such as polyphenol compounds, reduce the risk of heart disease, cancer and maintaining oral health. In the Province of Bangka Belitung Islands, there are tea from lowland plantation, known as Tayu Tea. This study aims to determine the differences in antioxidant activity and total phenol of Tayu Tea infusion and commercial brands of green and black tea infusions. The results showed that the antioxidant activity of Tayu Tea infusions (both black and green tea) was higher than the antioxidant activity of commercial infusions brands of green dan black tea. The total phenol content of Tayu black tea infusion was higher than the total phenol of commercial brands of black tea infusion, while the total phenolic content of Tayu green tea was lower than the total phenolic commercial brands of green tea infusion.

Keywords: Tayu Tea, Antioxidant Activity, Total Phenol, Commercial brands of tea

Topic: Public Health

[ABS-69]

Selected music has an effect on changes in a pulse just before odontectomy*Furaida Khasanah, Chyntia Ayu Nurlita, Eldarita*

Poltekkes Kemenkes Yogyakarta

Abstract

Odontectomy action cause psychological disorders in patients such as anxiety and trigger emotional changes. Several ways to reduce anxiety, one of which is non-pharmacological, namely relaxation. Music is a unique stimulus that influences the listener's physical and psychological responses and is an effective intervention of psychological relaxation. Purpose: To determine the differences in the use of selected music and non selected music towards change in a pulse just before odontectomy action was performed at the Medico Dental Center Yogyakarta. Method: This type of research is quasi-experimental with a total sampling technique of 26 female respondents aged 21 - 28 years and the first time doing odontectomy, 13 respondents in the selected music group, and 13 respondents in the non selected music group. This study uses Paired Sample T-Test hypothesis test. The mean pulse rate of the selected music group with pulse 73 - 85 decreased after being given the treatment, namely the initial pulse rate was 82.80 (85%) to 80.18 (85%), while the pulse rate 86-100 also experienced a decrease was from the initial pulse rate of 88.50 (92%) to 87.00 (87%). The mean pulse rate of the non selected music group with a pulse of 73 - 85 increased after being given the treatment, namely the initial pulse rate was 81.33 (85%) to 82.00 (84%), while the susceptible pulse from 86 to 100 experienced a decrease, namely which initially the averages pulse rate was 86.75 (88%) to 86.67 (88%). Conclusion: Selected music has an effect on changes in pulse rate.

Keywords: Odontectomy- selected music- pulse rate**Topic:** Nursing and anesthesiology

[ABS-70]

The potential effect of Torbangun (*Coleus amboinicus* Lour) leaves extract in decreasing of blood glucose levels and glutathione peroxidation activities in hyperglycemic rats model

Meilla Dwi Andrestian^{1*}, *Rizal Damanik*³, *Faisal Anwar*², *Nancy Dewi Yuliana*⁴

1 Department of Nutrition, Poltekkes Kemenkes Banjarmasin, Indonesia

2 Departemen of Community Nutrition, IPB University, Indonesia

3 South Asian Food and Agricultural Science and Technology, IPB University, Indonesia

4 Departemen of Food Science, IPB University, Indonesia

Abstract

Glutathione peroxidase (GSH-Px) is one of the earliest and most powerful antioxidant enzymes in cell. GSH-Px can be used as an indicator of oxidative stress in people with diabetes mellitus. This endogenous antioxidant is able to increase its activity by giving antioxidants contained in the Torbangun leaves extract. This study was an experimental study with a completely randomized design using 25 Sprague Dawley rats. Rats were divided into four groups, namely NG (negative control, hyperglycemic rats, seven rats), N (normal, six rats), H-IM (hyperglycemic, control of metformin drugs 62.5 mg/kgBW, six rats), and H-IT (hyperglycemics, extracts of Torbangun 620 mg/kgBW, six rats). The H-IT group received a treatment of Torbangun leaves extract and the H-IM group received a treatment of metformin for 14 days. Blood glucose were taken on days 0, 4th, 7th, 11th, and 14th and blood serum GSH-Px levels were taken after rats in necropsy on day 15th. GSH-Px levels were measured from rat blood serum that had been decropped on day 15th. The results showed an increase in GSH-Px activity in the group of H-IT rats by 33.10% compared to the group of NG rats and a significant decrease in blood glucose levels ($p = 0.005$). Torbangun leaves extract plays a role in decreasing blood glucose levels, repairing β -cells pancreas, and increasing blood serum GSH-Px levels of hyperglycemic rats.

Keywords: Torbangun- glutathione peroxidation- hyperglycemic

Topic: Nutrition and Dietetic

[ABS-71]

The effect of self-efficacy and subjective norm in motivating handwashing behavior among school students in Coastal Area*Nazliansyah1, Ashar Abilowo2*

Poltekkes Kemenkes Pangkalpinang

Abstract

Objectives: Hand washing is the most effective method of preventing the transmission of diseases through hands. The study objectives: To identify relationships between gender, availability of hand washing facilities, perception of self-efficacy toward hand washing compliance and subjective norm in implementing hand washing practice among students of public elementary school. Design: A cross sectional research study was used in this study. Methods: The multistage sampling technique was used for the sampling method in this study. First stages, the researcher used purposive sampling to identify the seven Public Elementary Schools in the coastal area of Belitung District. Further, the proportionate sampling and random sampling technique were employed in this study. Results: The results showed that 11.3% of the students were not hand washing properly. In regards of self-efficacy toward hand washing compliance also showed that was related to hand washing practice among elementary school students. Furthermore, subjective norm also was related to hand washing practice among elementary school students. The implication that Subjective norm has a significant relationship to hand washing behavior. Conclusions: Health care provider can develop specific intervention programs based on results to promote subjective norm among elementary school students since this norm or perception of norm can motivate hand washing behavior among elementary schools students effectively.

Keywords: Hand washing behavior, Self-efficacy. Subjective norm**Topic:** Nursing and anesthesiology

[ABS-72]

Relationship between feeding patterns and tooth brushing habits with dental caries in 8-10 yearsold children at Karangrejo 01 Semarang Elementary School*Kurnia Erma Puri (a)*, Supnawadi (b)*, Bq. Mutmainnah (c)**

Akademi Kesehatan Gigi Karya Adi Husada Mataram
Jl. Pahlawan Lingkar Selatan Komplek Perumahan Mapak Indah, Jempong Baru, Sekarbela,
Mataram, Nusa Tenggara Barat, Indonesia

Abstract

The diet should avoid foods and beverages that contains sugar or sucrose and foods that are soft and easily attached to the teeth(chocolate,biscuits) because it can cause demineralization of the enamel layer. The habit of brushing teeth incorrectly can cause dental caries. Caries incidence is associated with the level of sugar consumsion, if more often consume sugar of sweet foods there will be an increase in the incidence of dental caries. The purpose of this study was to determine the relationship between eating patterns and tooth brushing habits with the incidence of dental caries in children aged 8-10 years in Karangrejo 01 Elementary School Semarang. This type research is observasional analytic with design cross secyional. The population in the study were all students who were 8-10 years old at Karangrejo 01 Elementary School Semarang with a total sample of 60 people. Data collection instrumens used were questionnaires and examination sheets. Data analysis used is test statistic chi square. The results of the study with chi square, obtained results between dietary patterns with the incidence of caries which has a significant relationship with a p-value=0,000. The relationship between tooth brushing habits and caries events also had a significant with a p-value=0,001. So, it can be concluded that there is a relationship between diet and brushing habits with the incidence of caries in children aged 8-10 years in Karangrejo 01 Elementary School Semarang.

Keywords: Diet, Tooth Brushing Habits, Caries Occurrence**Topic:** Oral and Dental Health

[ABS-73]

Effect of consuming papaya fruit (carica papaya) on pH saliva in students class X and XI Madrasah Aliyah (MA) Puteri Al-Amin Martapura

Noor Syifa (1), Naning K Utami (1), Bunga Nurwati (1), Rasuna Ulfah (1), Siti Sabatul Habibah (1)

1) Dental Nursing Department, Health Polytechnic Of Banjarmasin, Banjarbaru, Indonesia

Abstract

Saliva becomes one of the components that affect the process of caries because saliva always wets the teeth so that it affects the environment in the oral cavity. The role of saliva in the caries process is related to demineralization and remineralization of hard tissue teeth or emails. Eating fibrous foods has many benefits, because the process of chewing fibrous foods will stimulate saliva production and have a *self-cleansing* effect on the mouth. Papaya has a high water content and fiber so by consuming papaya is expected to change the pH saliva. This study aims to find out the influence of consuming papaya fruit on pH saliva in students of grade X and XI Madrasah Aliyah (MA) Puteri Al-Amin Martapura. This type of research is pseudo-experimental research with the design of *one group pretest post-test*. Sampling with *Total Sampling* technique of 41 people. Analyze data with *Paired T-Test*. The result of the analysis with *Paired T-Test* test is $\rho = 0.003$ with a value of 0.05 ($\rho < \alpha$) which means there is an influence of consuming papaya fruit on pH saliva. In this study, it can be concluded that there is an influence of consuming papaya fruit on pH saliva in students of grade X and XI Madrasah Aliyah (MA) Puteri Al-Amin Martapura. It is recommended to consume fibrous and juicy fruits especially papaya because papaya can neutralize the pH of saliva.

Keywords: Papaya Fruit, pH Saliva

Topic: Oral and Dental Health

[ABS-74]

Marital age, cigarette exposure, physical activity, sleep duration and prenatal depression*Azniah Syam1*, Ashar HMI, and Eva Arna Abrar1*

Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Kesehatan Nani Hasanuddin Makassar

Abstract

Background: Extensive studies indicate that prenatal depression disrupts a woman's life and has a detrimental effect on the mother-child and further breastfeeding. Numerous factors associated with nutrition, physical activity, sleep patterns, and exposure to cigarette smoke are strongly suspected of contributing to the dysregulation of hormones associated with depression. Purpose: This study aims to examine the association between physical activity, nutritional status, and prior exposure to cigarette smoke and the risk of prenatal depression. Method: A cross-sectional study was conducted on 79 pregnant women at the Pampang Primary Healthcare Center between January and March 2021. Using chi-square and multiple logistic regression, identify the risk factors that most significantly contribute to the risk of prenatal depression. Result: Married under the age of 19th ($p < 0.039$), inactive daily exercise ($p < 0.023$), inadequate sleep duration ($p < 0.045$), and mothers who have been exposed to cigarette smoke for more than a year ($p < 0.001$) all increased the risk of prenatal depression. Cigarette exposure, contribute most, with a 5.4-fold increased risk of developing mental disorders while breastfeeding. Conclusion: It is critical for health services to include early screening for prenatal depression during antenatal care as a means of preventing future breastfeeding difficulties, particularly in mothers with vulnerability.

Keywords: cigarette exposure- marital age- nutritional status- physical activity- prenatal depression- risk factors

Topic: Public Health

[ABS-76]

Decrease anxiety third trimester on pregnancy - impact on hypnobirthing*Lutfiana Puspta Sari (a)*, Rosalinna(b)*

Poltekkes Kemenkes Surakarta

Abstract

Backgrounds: Most pregnant women experience worries, anxieties, and fears both during pregnancy, during labor and after delivery. Increased maternal psychological burden can cause problems with the quality of the fetus and complications that accompany the delivery process. Problems that are often experienced by pregnant women in the third trimester are anxiety and worry about the delivery process. Relaxation hypnobirthing is one of the non-pharmacological therapies that can be done to overcome psychological problems that often occur in the third trimester of pregnancy. Aim this study is to analyze the effect of hypnobirthing relaxation therapy on anxiety experienced by pregnant women in the third trimester of pregnancy. Methods: This study used a pre-experimental design with a pretest-posttest group design. It is used purposive sampling with 60 third trimester of pregnant woman as respondent. The data normality test uses the skewness value and the standard error results 2 so that the data distribution is normal. Test data analysis using Paired T-Test. Results: Bivariate analysis showed that p value of anxiety is 0.000 with the difference of mean is 7.41. Conclusion: There is an effect of hypnobirthing relaxation on reducing anxiety in third trimester pregnant women.

Keywords: anxiety, gravid, hypnobirthing**Topic:** Midwifery

[ABS-77]

The difference of in the inhibiton of essential oils of Kenikir Leaves (*Cosmos caudatus* Kunth.) and essential oils of Kemangi Leaves (*Ocimum basilicum*) on the growth of *Enterobacter aerogenes*

Ahmad Sukowaluyo¹, Anik Nuryati², Siti Zainatun Wasilah³ Amanda Retma A⁴

Department of Health Analyst, Poltekkes of the Ministry of Health Yogyakarta
Ngadinegaran MJ III / 62 Yogyakarta, Tel: (0274) 374200

Abstract

Diarrhea is an endemic disease in Indonesia which is often accompanied by death. One of the causes of diarrhea is the bacteria *Enterobacter aerogenes*. One of the plants that can be used as an antimicrobial is kenikir leaves (*Cosmos caudatus* Kunth.) And kemangi leaves (*Ocimum basilicum*) because they contain antibacterial compounds, one of which is essential oils. To find out the difference in the antibacterial potential produced from kenikir leaf essential oil and kemangi leaf essential oil, it is necessary to test the antibacterial sensitivity against the growth of *Enterobacter aerogenes* bacteria. Knowing the difference in the inhibition, sensitivity, effectiveness and avarage diameter of the inhibition zone of kenikir leaves (*Cosmos caudatus* Kunth.) Essential oil and kemangi leaves (*Ocimum basilicum*) essential oil on the growth of *Enterobacter aerogenes*. This research is a true experiment research with research design Post-test Only Control Group Design. The research subjects were *Enterobacter aerogenes* bacteria culture aged 1x24 hours old and the objects of research was kenikir leaves essential oil and kemangi leaves essential oil. The antibacterial inhibition test used the well diffusion method. The average comparison of the results of measuring the diameter of the inhibition zone of kenikir leaves essential oil, kemangi essential oil and tetracycline antibiotics were 15,47 mm, 13,95 mm and 25,27 mm. The mean difference of kenikir leaves essential oil was -9,8 mm (-14,47%) and -11,32 mm (-44,79%). The sensitivity of kenikir leaves essential oil and kemangi leaves essential oil is weak. The effectiveness of kenikir leaves essential oil is less effective and kemangi essential oil is not effective. Different test results there was a difference in the mean diameter of the inhibition zone of kenikir leaves essential oil and kemangi leaves essential oil on the growth of *Enterobacter aerogenes*.

Keywords: Kenikir Leaves Essential Oil, Kemangi Leaves Essential Oil, *Enterobacter aerogenes*, Inhibition

Topic: Medical Laboratory Technology

[ABS-78]

Potential of Kenikir (*Cosmos caudatus* Kunth) leaves essential oil against *Candida albicans* ATCC 10231 in vitro*Siti Zainatun Wasilah¹, Budi Martono², Wahyu Adi Pratama³**1,2,3) Jurusan Teknologi Laboratorium Medis Poltekkes Kemenkes Yogyakarta Ngadinegaran MJ III/62 Yogyakarta, 55143, Telp. (0274) 374200/375228 Email : Sitizainatun17@gmail.com*

POLTEKKES KEMENKES YOGYAKARTA

Abstract

Kenikir is a medicinal plant whose leaves are often consumed as vegetables. Kenikir leaves contain active compounds such as flavonoids, polyphenols, saponins, tannins, alkaloids and essential oils. These compounds are thought to be able to inhibit the growth of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and *Candida albicans* ATCC 10231 strains. The purpose of this study was to describe the effect of kenikir leaf essential oil on the growth of the *Candida albicans* ATCC 10231 strains. with 4 concentrations and 6 repetitions in *Candida albicans* and the concentration of kenikir leaf essential oil concentration of 0.5%, 1%, 1.5%, 2%. Data obtained in the form of inhibition zone diameter, were analyzed using Variant Analysis (Anova) and continued with Post Hoc test. The results showed that kenikir leaf essential oil at 1% could inhibit 0.5% essential oil concentration had a inhibition zone of 9.67 mm (moderate criteria)- essential oil concentration of 1% with a inhibition zone of 9.72 mm with criteria moderate and 1.5% concentration with inhibition zone 11.86% with strong criteria and concentration 2% with inhibition zone 12.67 mm with strong criteria all concentrations affect the growth of *Candida albicans* fungi with the most optimal concentration of 1.5% for the fungus *Candida albicans* ATCC 10231 strains. The results also showed that the higher the concentration of kenikir leaf extract, the inhibitory effect on the growth of *Candida albicans* ATCC 10231 strains was also higher.

Keywords: *Cosmos caudatus* Kunth, *Candida albicans* ATCC 10231 strains, diameter of the inhibition zone

Topic: Medical Laboratory Technology

[ABS-79]

Utilization Of Rice Bran (*Oryza sativa* L.) Situ Bagendit Variety as an alternative media for fungal growth *Trichophyton mentagrophytes**Ajeng Ayuning Tyas¹, Suyana², Siti Zainatun Wasilah³, Muhammad Burhanudin⁴*

Health Analyst Department, Health Polytechnic of Ministry of Health, Yogyakarta

Abstract

Identification of fungi requires culture or propagation through a growth medium. Media commonly used is Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) including instant media made by factories or companies in ready-to-use form, is expensive and can only be found in certain places so that an alternative medium that is easier to make and easy to obtain is rice bran media (*Oryza sativa* L.) Situ Bagendit variety. The utilization of rice bran as a growth medium for microorganisms is based on the nutritional components needed by the microorganisms. Rice bran (*Oryza sativa* L.) Situ Bagendit variety can be used as an alternative medium for the growth of *Trichophyton mentagrophytes*, the average diameter of growth of fungal colonies on rice bran media and PDA media, the effectiveness of fungal colony growth on rice bran media compared to PDA. Pre-experimental research with Static Group Comparison research design. Research subjects *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* with the research object of rice bran (*Oryza sativa* L.) Situ Bagendit variety. The results of measuring the diameter of the *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* colony on rice bran media mean 75.77 mm, the average colony diameter on PDA media is 75.52 mm. The difference in the mean colony diameter in rice bran media compared to PDA media was 0.25 mm or 0.33%. The effectiveness of growth is very effective. Rice bran (*Oryza sativa* L.) Situ Bagendit variety can be used as an alternative medium for the growth of *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* with 10% concentration.

Keywords: Effectiveness, Rice Bran, Alternative Media, Growth of *Trichophyton mentagrophytes*

Topic: Medical Laboratory Technology

[ABS-80]

Teacher satisfaction analysis of student practices department of dental nursing at Sdn Tembalang District*Fuji Lestari(a)*, Imam Supardan(b), Yodong(c)*

AKADEMI KESEHATAN GIGI KARYA ADI HUSADA MATARAM

Abstract

During the Field Learning Practice (PBL) students at SDN Tembalang District, Semarang City, head schools and teachers are happy with the existence of PBL students who provide a lot of experience to students about dental health and how to maintain dental and oral hygiene, so that students understand how to maintain their own oral and dental health aims to find out how the description of teacher satisfaction with the practice of majoring students Dental Nursing at the Semarang Ministry of Health Poltekkes at SDN Tembalang District. This research uses cross sectional method using descriptive analytic design. The number of samples in this study as many as 74 respondents taken using the Slovin formula. The results of the study showed that most of the respondents stated they were satisfied with the. Factor availability of health services provided by students majoring in dental nursing with percentage of 70% (52 respondents), on the health service achievement factor respondents feel satisfied with the services provided with a percentage of 93% (69 respondents), on the the affordability of health services respondents are satisfied with the services provided by the percentage of 86% (64 respondents), while the effectiveness and efficiency of health services most respondents were satisfied with the services provided with a percentage of 71% (53 (respondents), and on the quality of health services, respondents were satisfied with the services provided given with a percentage of 91% (67 respondents). It is suggested that students can increase dental and oral health services to students and teachers in primary schools.

Keywords: Teacher satisfaction, student practice**Topic:** Oral and Dental Health

[ABS-81]

Knowledge of teenage girls on breast self-examination behavior (BSE)*Rohani Siregar*

Bachelor of Midwifery Study Program, Medika Suherman University, Cikarang Bekasi –
Indonesia
rohanisiregar81@gmail.com

Abstract

Breast Self-Examination (BSE) is an early detection of breast cancer that can be done by teenage girl since early stage. Early detection of breast cancer can reduce mortality by 25-30%. The results of a preliminary study of 6 teenage girls there are 4 young women who have never practiced BSE routinely after menstruation. This type of research is a quantitative survey, with a cross sectional approach. The population in this study were all Teenage Girls Class X SMK Negeri 2 Karawang. Sampling was carried out in total population with a sample of 150 respondents. Data was collected by distributing questionnaires using google form. The data analysis technique used was univariate and bivariate with chi square test. Univariate analysis showed that of the 150 respondents studied there were 96 respondents (64%) who had low knowledge, and 126 people (84%) of class X teenage girls had never done BSE. Chi square statistical test showed a significant relationship between knowledge about breast self-examination (BSE) and BSE behavior with a p value of 0.02. It was concluded that there was a need for counseling from health workers about reproductive health for teenage girl, especially about the practice of breast self-examination (BSE), as an early detection of breast cancer.

Keywords: Knowledge, Behavior, BSE

Topic : Midwifery

[ABS-82]

Oscillated traction and mandibular condylar movement exercise to decrease disability of internal derangement TMJ*Luluk Maulina (a), Arfian Hamzah (b)*

a) Bachelor Physiotherapy Study Program, Medika Suherman University
Jalan Raya Industri Pasir gombong, Kec. Cikarang Utara, Bekasi, Jawa Barat 17530

b) D3 Physiotherapy Study Program, Politeknik Unggulan Kalimantan
Jalan Pangeran Hidayatullah No.10 RT.14, Benua Anyar, Sungai Jingah, Kec.
Banjarmasin Utara, Kota Banjarmasin, Kalimantan Selatan 70122

Abstract

Internal derangement Temporomandibular Joint (TMJ) is a disturbance in the TMJ where there is a displacement of the normal functional relationships of the discus with the mandibular condyle and the articular part of the temporal bone, where there is a change in the pattern of motion of the disc (painfull arc) that makes changes in motion pattern C or S. This study aims to prove the decrease in disability by administering oscillated traction and mandibular condylar movement exercise (MCME). The design of this study is pre test-post test group design. 10 patients were given oscillated traction and mandibular condylar movement exercise also given 3 times a week for 2 weeks. Measurement test of decreased disability using Temporomandibular Disorder Disability Index (TDI). The results of this study indicate that MCME can significantly to decrease disability in the condition of internal derangement of the temporomandibular joint ($p=0.001$). It is recommended that physiotherapists apply it to patients with conditions of internal derangement of the temporomandibular joint to reduce disability.

Topic: Public Health

[ABS-83]

Monitoring analysis of the speed of outpatient medical record services at Sentra Medika Cikarang Hospital, Bekasi Regency, 2021

Afif Wahyudi Hidayat
Medika Suherman University

Abstract

One of the quality of outpatient services in hospitals is the provision of fast and accurate medical record files so that they can support good health services. Provision of medical record documents in outpatient services in accordance with Hospital Minimum Service Standards No.129/Menkes/SK/II/2008 that is less than or equal to 10 minutes, but to determine the continuity of the time suitability, monitoring analysis needs to be carried out, whether there is an increase in speed of medical record services or experiencing a decline in medical record services. So if there are significant obstacles, it is necessary to look for the causative factors, then if the speed of service increases, it is necessary to know and improve what factors greatly influence the increase of speed in medical record services of the outpatient unit of Sentra Medika Cikarang Hospital. The purpose of this study is to monitor and analyze the speed of medical record services in the outpatient unit of Sentra Medika Hospital Cikarang. The type of research conducted is qualitative research. The subject of this research is the coordinator in each part of processing (assembling, coding, indexing, analyzing), distribution, filling or storage and retrieval of medical records. The results of this study indicate that the human resources in the medical record unit in the filling division have not divided the workload based on the number of available resources and there is no written job description and there is still a lack of training in the filling / storage and retrieval of medical record documents. There are still medical record documents that have not been stored properly on the storage rack, and there are still borrowed medical record documents that have not been returned within 1 x 24 hours at the medical record section. Management of medical records must be regulated properly, so as to produce speed of quality medical record services in outpatient units.

Topic : Medical Record and Health Information

[ABS-84]

The impact of the dating scene on teenagers' premarital sexual activity in Karawang Regency, IndonesiaErmaya Sari Bayu Ningsih¹⁾

¹⁾Undergraduate Midwifery Study Program Institut Medika Drg. SUherman; Raya Industri Street Pasir GombongJababeka North Cikarang, West Java 17530
E-mail: ^{a)}mayapendi3969@gmail.com ^{b)}ermaya@imds.ac.id

Abstract

Courtship into the beginning of sexual behavior as kissing, necking, petting, and intercourse. These behaviors can lead to a teenager for having sexual intercourse, Data from the Indonesian Child Protection Commission in 2013 shows that as many as 43% of teenagers have had premarital sex. Research objectives that is analyzing the influence of the dating scene against premarital sex in adolescents in Karawang Regency. Closer look at the research by the quantitative methods research sexual behavior assume that the prenuptial agreement can be resolved and grouped into data or information cause and effect sectional designed cross research. The data over interview, observation through the questionnaire juvenile on inclusion ever being relationships courtship. Analysis undertaken with the approach of the survey sampling. Research show a prenuptial agreement in risky sexual behavior date as many as 63.2 %. There are the relation between the ages of significant influence, sex, the role of parents there are significant impact on premarital sexual behavior. Be hoped there will be the role of all parties the teenager, parents, school stakeholders can support the prevention of sexual behavior prenuptial agreement is at risk.

Keywords: Danting, Influence, Behavior, Prenuptial Agreement, Sexual Teenagers

Topic: Midwifery

BOOK OF ABSTRACT

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